

D2.2 – REPORT ON THE DEEP ROOTS OF SOCIAL CONTRACT

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List of abbreviations

AKP	Justice and Development Party
CO3	COntinuous COnstruction of Resilient Social COntracts through Societal Transformations
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HDZ	Croatian Democratic Union [<i>Hrvatska demokratska zajednica</i>]
HRBiH	High Representative for Bosnia and Herzegovina
IDP	Internally Displaced People
ILO	International Labor Organization
LGBTQ+	Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, and other
M	Month
MFA	<i>Movimento das Forças Armadas</i> [Armed Forces' Movement]
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organization
NDH	Independent State of Croatia
NSDAP	<i>Nationalsozialistische Deutsche Arbeiterpartei</i> [National Socialist German Workers' Party]
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
PKK	Kurdistan Workers' Party
PREC	<i>Processo Revolucionário em Curso</i> [Ongoing Revolutionary Process]
SC	Social Contract
SDP	Social Democrat Party
T	Task
UN	United Nations
US	United States
WP	Work Package
WWI	World War I
WWII	World War II

List of Consortium partners

Table 1. List of Consortium partners

No	Role	Short name	Legal name	Country
1	COO/ BEN	UH	HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO	FI
2	BEN	UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITET	SE
3	BEN	CES	CENTRO DE ESTUDOS SOCIAIS	PT
4	BEN	CLS	FONDATSIYA TSENTAR ZA LIBERALNI STRATEGII	BG
5	BEN/ COO	DRI	DEMOS HELSINKI OY	FI
6	BEN	HFD	HOCHSCHULE FULDA-UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES	DE
7	BEN	IBU	ISTANBUL BILGI UNIVERSITESI	TR
8	BEN	UNIZG	SVEUCILISTE U ZAGREBU FAKULTET POLITICKIH ZNANOSTI	HR
9	BEN	AUP	THE AMERICAN UNIVERSITY OF PARIS	FR
10	BEN	UCU	HIGHER EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENT UKRAINIAN CATHOLIC UNIVERSITY	UA

Executive summary

Related documents	
Other CO3 deliverables	D2.1 Report of the theoretical mapping, the EU construction of SC, polarisation and the impact and legacy of colonialism D2.3 The CO3 Framework D3.1 Report of country-case methodology

The Report on the deep roots of the social contract introduces the perspective of historical empires and authoritarian regimes on European Social Contracts. It is one of three CO3 deliverables for Work Package (WP) 2 – Theory and CO3 model development. It thus complements: D2.1 – Report on the theoretical mapping, the EU construction of social contract polarisation and the impact and legacy of colonialism; and D2.3 – The CO3 Framework. Together, these achieve the WP2 objective of building the foundation of the CO3 model by generating an in-depth theoretical understanding of the formation, limits and scope of social contracts, as well as how they impact their current underpinnings. The key insights from these deliverables inform the theoretical and historical key points, to be further developed in, and applied to, the following work packages.

The Report is based on the work developed under T2.4 – Uncover the deep roots of the CO3 social contracts: empires to nation-states to the EU. The inquiry about the impact and legacy of empires and authoritarian regimes on European Social Contracts was based on desk research outlining: the legacies of different empires and authoritarian regimes to specific contemporary (national) social contracts; how the social contract has been negotiated in the CO3 countries; the deep roots of European Social Contracts.

The contextualisation of the different case-countries in which the CO3 project undergoes empirical research is presented in the report. The eleven CO3 country-cases analysed – Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Portugal, Sweden, Türkiye and Ukraine – are headed by teams of ten institutions. CES coordinated the task and drafted the report based on the contributions given by all Consortium partners through their country profiles. Contributions are diverse, inter-, multi- and pluri-disciplinary, thus providing a multifaceted analysis of the deep roots of the social contract. This relates also to the CO3 methodological pluralism identified in D3.1 – Report of country-case methodology, and the empirical work to be developed in other CO3 WPs.

Based on the analysis of all country-cases, the Report provides an interpretative framework elucidating the predominant factors, consequences and dynamics of the evolution of the social contract within the various countries under scrutiny, and within the broader European Union context. Additionally, it also proposes an exercise of methodological cross-fertilization that provides a long view on the processes analysed that extends beyond the geographical and temporal boundaries of their original contexts.

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Introduction

The Report on the deep roots of the social contract of the research project CO3 - COntinuous COnstruction of resilient social COntracts through societal transformations (deliverable D2.2) provides an overview of the impact and legacy of empires and authoritarian regimes on European Social Contracts. This report is based on the work carried out in Task T2.4 – Uncover the deep roots of the CO3 social contracts: empires to nation-states to the EUrope [M5-M12], in which all Consortium partners took part.

This is the second of three deliverables produced in Work Package (WP) 2 – Theory and CO3 model development. This deliverable aims at building the foundation of the CO3 model via generating an in-depth theoretical understanding of the formation, limits and scope of social contracts, as well as how they impact their current underpinnings. The WP focuses on the deep roots of the social contract and includes an analysis of the CO3 case studies. This theoretical and historical analysis provides a precise definition of what is meant by a social contract in this project, as well as a basis for the development of future WPs. Within this WP, task T2.4 asks about the impact and legacy of empires and authoritarian regimes on European Social Contracts. The task was performed through desk research on all country-cases, outlining the legacies of different empires and authoritarian regimes to their respective social contracts and how social contracts have been negotiated in the CO3 levels (for more information on the CO3 levels, see D2.3 – The CO3 Framework). The focus on empires is strongly related to the legacy of authoritarian regimes within and between each country. This legacy is, therefore, another core root of European Social Contracts. The eleven CO3 country-cases analysed in this report – Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Portugal, Sweden, Türkiye and Ukraine – are headed by teams of ten institutions.¹

It should also be noted that the report is founded on the expertise of a multi- and interdisciplinary team, and it thus follows and employs the established 'methodological pluralism' that characterises the CO3 project. As outlined in D3.1, entitled "Report of country case methodology", CO3 fosters the epistemological and ontological diversity of the team. While cognisant of the fact that comparability may be limited by this approach, such a framing provides a more nuanced and diverse understanding of the nature and dynamics of European

¹ More information on the country-cases is available at: <https://www.co3socialcontract.eu/about>. CES coordinated the task and drafted the report based on the contributions provided by all Consortium partners.

social contracts in the country-cases under analysis. Indeed, in a project of this nature, methodological pluralism allows for an articulation of the intricacy of our arguments and facilitates the discernment of salient analytical points.

Furthermore, it is imperative to comprehend the emphasis on the deep roots within the post-foundational approach of the CO3 theoretical framework (see D2.1 and D2.3). As highlighted in our overview of the history of the social contract (D2.1), the foundational assumptions of the idea of the social contract have lately been relaxed or even transformed. The standpoint critiques of Pateman (1988) and Mills (1997), focusing respectively on issues of gender and race in/and the social contract, made strides towards this post-foundational approach. Still, crucial in this scope is the work of Laclau and Mouffe (1985). The latter offers crucial insights on how social contracts can be formed, contested, and maintained or shifted, as hegemonic arrangements. Considered through this lens, social contracts no longer needlessly take on a foundational nature, whereby their current arrangements were grounded on likewise “deep roots” and strictly similar structural processes. Instead, social contracts ought to be encircled “post-foundationally” as constantly evolving, consenting, and spatial-temporally contingent relationships between those holding power and the citizenry. This has broad implications for how social contracts should be researched (comparatively; see D3.1); and more specifically, it also shapes how the exercise of investigating and presenting the “deep roots” of the social contract espoused here must take place. In sum, this report does not presuppose the existence of a specific foundational historical juncture at which the genesis of the contemporary social contracts in European countries can be traced. Instead, by assuming the ongoing and contextualized processes of construction of the social contract, the report evidences the sequential occurrences of the most impactful historical events in the different country cases, while also highlighting how these historical legacies contribute to characterise the present social contract in European countries, and at the EU level. Consequently, a range of asymmetrical temporalities is implied, with country teams providing reports on the most paradigmatic transitions in their respective societies and focusing on how such legacies draw on political, social and economic inequalities.

The approach for selecting key historical events is close to Koselleck’s theory of multiple temporalities (2007, 2005). It combines the synchronic (historical present) and diachronic (impacts over time) dimensions of the events highlighted, considering their relationship with the evolving social contracts. The country-reports provide a big picture of the multiple temporal layers that frame the ‘historical time’ (Koselleck, 2005), and which interact with each other. They comprise short-term events, medium-term structures (political regimes, institutions, economies) and long-term continuities (languages, mindsets and social orders) (Koselleck, 2007, 2005). Read altogether, the country cases show how similar processes (e.g., transition

from the Ancient Regime to Liberalism; emergence of nation-states; industrialization; rise and fall of authoritarian and totalitarian regimes; democratization processes; among others) did not take place synchronically in the different territories/political entities addressed. Thus, it gives us a historically situated understanding of how changes occurred in different regions of Europe.

It is important to capture these asymmetric temporalities for understanding the political construction of the European Union as a system of differentiated integration, which combines distinct levels and paces of interdependence, differentiation and politicization (Schimmelfennig et al, 2015). The Schengen area, the internal market, the monetary union or the common foreign and security policy are examples of policy areas where that approach was followed. One may see differentiation as a core feature of European integration, which has been consolidated with the deepening and widening of the EU powers, as the policy scope and membership were growing (*ibid.*).

In sum, the report's aim is thus twofold: firstly, to examine the deep roots of the 'Continuous Construction of Social Contracts' in the various country-cases under analysis; secondly, to analyse the societal impact of the deep roots on political, social and economic inequalities in the different countries and at the European level.

To achieve these goals, for each of the eleven country-cases under study, the Report includes an expanded overview, which provides a brief historical contextualisation in articulation with imperialism, colonialism (broadly understood as any form of foreign domination; but, see below for a note on these concepts) and authoritarianism. Based on this overview, the deep roots of the inequalities of the current social contract in each country-case are examined by focusing on present-day political, social and economic inequalities. This framework offers a comprehensive understanding of how imperialism, colonialism and authoritarianism shaped the evolution of the social contract throughout different ages in eleven European countries. Furthermore, this framework illustrates how the social contract generated specific political, social and economic inequalities in distinct historical contexts and geographies. The focus on how the “deep roots” of the countries’ social contracts affect current political, economic and social inequalities is crucial for furthering the overall aims of the CO3 project. This is especially key from the perspective of the EU and its future configurations. Such inequalities, alongside the challenges inherent to the contemporary environmental crisis and the establishment of ecosocial contracts, are putting pressures on the resilience of European social contracts. And the wealth of trajectories offered by the historical legacies of each country, and the specific inequalities they have generated, place differential challenges on the possibility of sustaining support for, and obtaining, EU-level social contracts. This is why, in the general overview, as well as in the individual country profiles, we have focused on both the causes (deep roots) of

European social contracts, and the (social, environmental) outcomes of those configurations in terms of political, economic and social inequalities.

The imperial backgrounds analysed vary from overseas colonialism or continental imperialism, to positions as colonising powers or colonised territories.² Finally, a common perspective on crossing topics addressed by all partners is presented, including political regime changes and shifts in constitutional, colonial, imperial and/or authoritarian frameworks. This perspective attempts to build an interpretative grid of analysis on the evolutionary patterns of the social contract and how it has been negotiated in the CO3 countries. This backdrop provides valuable insights for future tasks, namely, those involving the conceptualisation of the CO3 model.

The contextualisation of the different case-countries in which the CO3 project undergoes empirical research is based on diverse contributions aimed at reflecting the distinct features of each country. This perspective illuminates the most salient characteristics of each country's historical trajectory in relation to the evolution of the social contract, also presenting an overview of the main inequalities stemming from the historical conditions depicted for each country. The identification of these characteristics, outcomes, and historical milestones is informed by a deliberative selection process, involving the research team responsible for each country's analysis.

The document is organised into three sections. Firstly, the systematic analysis of the country-cases is assessed focusing on the main points highlighted in each country-case regarding the articulation of the social contract with colonialism, imperialism and authoritarianism, as well as the impact of the deep-root legacies in their current socio-political contexts. Views expressed on each country's contribution summarize the historical interpretation of its authors and not the Consortium as a whole. However, country reports were discussed in plenary workshops and methodological pluralism was aligned with the post-foundational perspective of the project justified prior. This section is followed by a concise 'Cross-fertilising analysis of the deep roots of European Social Contracts', in which points of conjuncture and difference across cases are identified and debated. Thus, overall, the objective of these first sections is to provide an interpretative framework elucidating the predominant factors, consequences and dynamics of the social contract's evolution across the various countries under study, and within the broader EU context. This reflection also results from workshop activities organised within the CO3

² In some cases, depending on the respective historical contexts and historiographic interpretations, the concept of colonialism is not used.

project in February 2025, with a special focus on the deep roots of the social contract, where all partners participated.

Lastly, the report expands on the previous overviews and presents a more detailed analysis of each of the country-cases, focusing on: a) an historical overview of the entanglement of imperialism/colonialism and authoritarianism within the evolution of the social contract, and b) a selective reflection on the most significant outcomes related to current political, social and economic inequalities. Overall, this common structure aims for a sufficient level of consistency and comparability between the countries' contributions. For each country-case, the literature consulted to inform the text is listed in the references, as a relevant starting point for further analyses.

Imperialist and colonial roots (a brief note on concepts)

This report focuses on imperialism as a form of state control over a foreign entity, encompassing social, cultural, political, territorial and/or economic rule. To this extent, the definition of imperialism favoured here is open-ended, politically and historically contingent, and includes different forms of colonialism, influence, domination, hegemony, foreign dependence, protectorate, shared sovereignty and dynastic union, amongst others. This approach allows shedding light on the socio-political and economic inequalities related to the history of distinct contemporary European Empires.

This overview also uncovers different conceptual interpretations and narratives about historical experiences and forms of external domination. Examples range from overseas colonialism (Portuguese and French Empires), through different arrangements of continental Empires (Soviet Union, Nazism, Habsburg/Austro-Hungarian Empire and Ottoman Empire), to cases of international monitoring (Dayton Agreement in Bosnia-Herzegovina).

As the nature of this document discourages adopting the perspective of the conceptual history, the conceptual approach presented here attempts to deal with the complexity of addressing how political and social concepts changed in meaning over time. Using the concept of colonialism when talking of the history of some European regions is particularly challenging. In the context of different continental Empires is it more suitable to consider them as cases of internal colonialism, settler colonialism, or colonialism through the territorial expansion towards neighbouring territories? Can we consider Hungary (after 1956) a soviet colony? We are aware that these (and other) are some examples of questions that could be raised; albeit noteworthy, the discussion of these specific issues goes beyond the scope of this report and is, hence, not pursued here.

In effect, some cases also illustrate the dynamics related to using different theoretical frameworks to analyse historical events. One case regards Ottoman Imperialism. It has been argued that the Ottoman Empire did not have colonies, while its African policies have been described as ‘borrowed colonialism’. The Ottoman state was more concerned with internal control and consolidation, rather than with overseas colonial expansion, pursuing administrative centralisation and integrating its provinces into the political system. Another case relates to the Swedish influence and political control of Finland, and the ongoing discussion (in Finland) as to whether this constituted colonialism or mere hegemony.

For the sake of clarity, Imperialism is here treated broadly to touch on several ramifications. It may be used when referring to ‘formal imperialism’ – related to the “explicit transfer of sovereignty and, usually, the imposition of direct administrative control” – or “informal imperialism” that concerns the “links created by trade, investment or diplomacy”, according to the distinction proposed by Nicolaïdis et al. (2015, p. 3).

Mostly, the concept of Empire is treated in this report as a type of state. Other political forms addressed are nation-states, federations, confederations or semi-autonomous kingdoms, principalities and gran-duchies. This plurality of cases manifests the coexistence between different types of states and systems of government. A diverge range is covered, from ancient forms of government to contemporary ones, such as democracies – republic or constitutional monarchies –, authoritarian or totalitarian regimes.

Synthesis of the deep roots of the social contract in CO3 Countries

The expanded overview of the deep roots of the social contact in the CO3 cases provides important historical and context-sensitive information about the eleven countries studied.

Some relevant historical events and processes are highlighted considering the extent to which they contributed to major shifts in the respective countries' social contract. For each country, these events will be narratively summarized in the next few paragraphs. At the end of this section, a table will provide a compared and systematic overview, including the main events, occurrences, periods, and current impacts of these deep root legacies.

Countries

Across history, the territory of **Bosnia-Herzegovina** has been annexed repeatedly as part of different imperial endeavours: Ottoman Empire (mid-15th century until the late 19th century), Austro-Hungarian Empire (until WWI), Kingdom of Yugoslavia (after WWI) and finally the Social Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (after WWII, until its independence in 1992). Nazi occupation also occurred during WWII. Bosnian nationalism developed significantly under Austro-Hungarian rule and was further reinforced within Yugoslavia. However, even if the previous colonial experiences are over, new forms of imperialism and external interference are shaping the social contract of the country (e.g., EU integration and Dayton Agreements). Overall, its long imperial history has created a multi-ethnic and multi-religious society in which internal frictions went from periods of open dispute to others marked by latent tension. Also, political and ethnic tensions, including recent calls for secession from the Republika Srpska, have been spreading increased fear of further Balkanisation in the region.

After five centuries under Ottoman rule, **Bulgaria** became a sovereign independent state in 1908. This (re)established Bulgarian state included a sizable Turkish ethnic minority. In the 1930s, popular revolts followed by violent coups, and the abolition of political parties, solidified Bulgaria's authoritarian turn, legitimised by its perceived role in stabilising the country. On the eve of WWII, a notable rapprochement occurred between Bulgaria and Nazi Germany. During WWII, Bulgaria administered Yugoslav and Greek territories (1941-1944) after Nazi Germany invaded the region. In 1944, the Soviet army occupied Bulgaria, and after the end of WWII, a communist regime was installed in the country. The period from 1944 until 1947 was marked by communist-sponsored violence and constant political interference. Bulgaria's totalitarian regime (1947-1954) gradually transformed into an authoritarian one, until the fall of the communist regime (1989). With the end of the communist regime, most Bulgarian citizens were involved in the formation of the new social contract, including ethnic Turks through their representatives. But the Roma minority were de facto excluded as they lacked group-specific political representation. Due to the country's authoritarian and socialist past, the consensus for a transition to democracy included the economic liberalisation of Bulgaria.

Croatia became part of the Hungarian kingdom in 1102 and until 1939, a long period when the territory did not experience any significant administrative autonomy. In the 16th century, the Kingdom of Hungary (which included the 'Croatian lands') became part of the Habsburg Monarchy, first, and later of the Austro-Hungarian empire. After WWI, 'Croatian lands' became part of the Kingdom of Serbs, Croats and Slovenes, which became the Kingdom of Yugoslavia in 1929. An expanded variant of the Croatian Banovina territory was set up as the Independent State of Croatia (NDH) in 1941, by the extreme-nationalist and catholic Ustasha movement, with the assistance of the German occupation army. Croatia was part of communist Yugoslavia from 1945 to 1991. Political and ethnic questions fuelled the independence war that ended successfully in 1995. Political life then was largely determined by tensions between Serbs and Croats, which occasionally resulted in political violence and murders. After the war, meaningful efforts have been undertaken to improve these minorities' political and economic rights. To this day, Serbs remain the largest ethnic minority.

The history of **Finland** is deeply entwined with the imperial struggles of its two powerful neighbours: Sweden and Russia. This historical experience shaped its national identity and political strategies, fostering a policy of neutrality or non-alliance and resilience. For example, a defensive mindset is deeply embedded in the Finnish identity. In the late 19th century, Finland found itself navigating a delicate balance between building political and democratic institutions and simultaneously resisting Russian rule. This tension culminated in the sweeping parliamentary reform of 1906, a defining moment that introduced universal suffrage and reshaped the nation's political framework. Despite the turmoil of the 1918–1919 Civil War, Finland managed to uphold its parliamentary democracy, an achievement that set it apart from many other nations grappling with internal divisions. However, the Finnish state has long engaged in practices that resemble colonialism towards Sámi people (for example, limiting Sámi land rights, imposing Finnish-language education, failing to fully recognise Sámi self-governance). This history continues to shape current debates over land use, environmental policies and minority rights. Overall, the legacies of imperial rule are still visible in Finland's legislative and institutional frameworks, as well as in its linguistic and cultural landscapes. Swedish influence is dominant in the West, while Russian legacies are more pronounced in the East. Finland's military culture also still plays a key role in shaping national discourse. The need for self-defence against potential colonial or imperialist threats from Russia has fostered a strong emphasis on national security. Recently, this concern has been shown in the rapid shift from non-alliance to NATO membership.

France's vast colonial empire, spanning Africa, Asia and the Americas, embedded hierarchical structures within its social contract. The doctrine of "civilising lesser races" coexisted uneasily with the country's revolutionary ideals of fraternity, liberty and equality. The

developmental disparities currently found between the *Métropole* and its overseas territories still reflect this colonial neglect. The Colonial authoritarianism practiced by France intensified this, imposing stark divides between the colonisers and colonised, with racial and cultural superiority as its bedrock. This colonial inheritance ignites persistent struggles over identity, equity and belonging, fractionalizing contemporary French society. The Algerian War's brutal legacy and the fraught process of decolonisation also remain etched in the country's collective memory. Thus, France's relationship with its former African colonies remains complex and even marked by (neo)colonialism. On the international stage, France's interventions in Africa, such as its military presence in Mali, evoke colonial echoes, raising questions about neocolonialism. Going beyond its colonial presence, France's history is also marked by a tradition of centralised, authoritarian governance, from Louis XIV's absolutism to Napoleon's militarised state and the Vichy regime's collaborationist repression. Even the French Revolution, despite its democratic aspirations, took authoritarian turns, as seen in the Reign of Terror. This centralisation also extended into its colonial administration, where France ruled with rigid control, suppressing dissent as seen in the 1945 Sétif massacre in Algeria. The Fifth Republic, established in 1958 by Charles de Gaulle, continues this tradition of centralisation, with a strong presidency that prioritises state sovereignty over regional autonomy. Historical authoritarianism has, in sum, birthed a dual legacy: a deep-seated expectation that the state will act as a guarantor of welfare, education and security, coupled with a counter current of scepticism and resistance.

The unification of **Germany**, under Prussian dominion in the late 19th century, was built on an imperial authoritarian state with strong military power and a potent agrarian-aristocratic elite. Nationalism played a crucial role in overcoming traditional regional forms of identification, while conjuring images of the 'enemy' became the prime means for constructing a German national identity. Imperial Germany's colonial rule, albeit short (1848-1920), culminated in the first genocide of the 20th century against the resisting Nama and Herero in southwestern Africa (today's Namibia). Another landmark moment of this colonial period was the Berlin 'Africa Conference' in 1884, which gathered representatives from 15 imperial powers, with the aim of agreeing rules for further colonising Africa and staking out their claims to ownership. Not a single representative from Africa itself was present and the consequences for the continent still linger today. The rise of Adolf Hitler and the Nazi Party (NSDAP) in 1933 marked a radical return to authoritarianism. Under Nazi rule (1933-1945), Germany pursued a radical expansionist policy, rooted on racial ideology. Germany only retained partial sovereignty and was integrated into Europe after its defeat in WWII. The reception of the German past is mainly shaped by the legacy of National Socialism, the Holocaust and later state socialism in Eastern Germany (1945-1990). Today, reunified Germany is confronted, not only with a clash of very

different memories that are deeply rooted, but also with vastly different cultures and politics of memory. The specific nature of reunification (which occurred as an incorporation of East Germany into the existing legal, political and economic structure of West Germany) added a decisive layer of inequality to the German social fabric. Today, Germany's political culture remains shaped by its authoritarian past. Debates continue about historical responsibility, state power and democratic resilience, in the face of rising populism and extremism.

Hungary, as the Kingdom of Hungary, was an independent entity from the 11th to the 16th century, mainly claiming allegiance to Western Christianity (Rome). However, after that period, the history of Hungary is characterized by long foreign dominance occurring under Ottoman rule, Habsburg rule, and (later) Soviet influence. The post-WWI days were ones characterized by the fragmentation of the country's territory. The Treaty of Trianon, which stripped Hungary of two-thirds of its territory, was framed as an imperial restructuring of Central Europe. This loss led to irredentist sentiments that persist in Hungarian politics today. The Soviet Republic established after WWI, led by Béla Kun, was a short-lived experience. This government was crushed, which led to anti-communist legislation. In the interwar period, Hungary lived under authoritarian rule, led by Miklós Horthy, whose regime mirrored Mussolini's more than Hitler's. After WWII, Soviet troops stationed in Hungary's territory between 1949 and 1990, and the country was put under the Soviet sphere of influence. After the post-socialist transition, a process of gradual integration in Euro-Atlantic organisations unfolded, resulting in Hungary's accession to NATO (late 1990s) and the EU (2004). The Orbán regime is considered an electoral autocracy, where elections take place, but in the context of breaking down democracy, the rule of law and fundamental rights. The public sphere is controlled to the extent that political change is very hard to achieve. Under Viktor Orbán's rule, the government appears to employ implicit exclusions – particularly of women and Roma – while drawing political support from rural communities. People belonging to the LGBTQ community are citizens excluded from the social contract. Furthermore, ethnic diversity remains a fraught issue. The Roma minority represents the largest national minority, with 2.5% of the population officially identifying as such in the 2022 census. However, systemic discrimination likely leads to underreporting.

Portugal's social contract evolved with political and social changes, alongside the Portuguese Colonial Empire. The imperialization of the nation was established to boost national identity and legitimise different political regimes by promoting people's consent. The end of the Estado Novo and the colonial empire, along with the establishment of democracy and European integration, are founding pillars of the current Portuguese social contract. Historical events rupturing the prevailing political and social order were also nodal points reinforcing the links between colonialism and the social contract. Besides the economic question, the political (and

symbolic) dimensions of maintaining the colonies were decisive for various political regimes. Colonialism influenced the definition of national policy and politics, as well as the survival of the regime itself. The cost-benefit ratio of the colonies has been questioned at different times by historians and economists. Colonial trade and the wealth it created, as well as the human resources required for colonial exploitation, prevented the efficient use of the Portuguese territory and its economic development. Portuguese decolonisation and democratisation are characterised by their radical and revolutionary dimensions, as well as by a strong military tutelage. This influence is due to the legitimisation granted to the Armed Forces Movement, which was the driving force of the 25th of April (1974) coup, resulting in the overthrow of the Estado Novo authoritarian regime. The Carnation Revolution (ending 48 years of dictatorship) enabled the enshrinement of fundamental freedoms and guarantees, as well as political, economic, cultural and social rights, including freedom of expression. Historically, colonialism generated distinct migration flows within the imperial space, including: white settlers, enslaved peoples, colonial administrators and civil servants, military personnel and forced labourers, among others. This space created regimes of oppression and differentiation, generating manifold exclusions. Those regimes are articulated with socio-economic inequalities, faced by people from the former colonised territories, coming to Portugal in the decades following decolonisation. These inequalities include access to employment, the labour market, decent housing, education, justice and healthcare.

During its imperial phase (1611-1721), **Sweden** was established as a regional power through different national state unions. The country had complex relations with neighbouring powers, with the present area of Finland being a part of Sweden, lacking its own administrative structures or linguistic autonomy. The country's foray into overseas colonialism, though very limited in extent and time (1638-1663 and 1784-1878), was also initiated during the Empire era. The kingdom of Sweden held small colonies in Africa, Asia and the Americas, namely the island of Saint Barthélemy in the Caribbean. Internally, Sweden's early embrace of press freedom set a precedent for democratic values, with the 1766 Swedish Freedom of the Press Act recognised as the first of its kind. There was also early democratisation in the form of a constitutional monarchy and universal suffrage (1921). However, such developments occurred alongside the forced cultural assimilation and Christianisation of the Sámi people during the 19th century. In the early 20th century, these minorities also suffered discrimination due to the popularity of racial hygiene ideas in Sweden, when both the Sámi people and the Finns were racialised. Industrial growth absorbed hundreds of thousands of immigrants in the 1970s. At first, most came from Finland, which was still grappling with the economic consequences of WWII. Other groups of immigrants came from Italy, as well as former Yugoslavian and Middle Eastern countries. Due to unsuccessful integration policies and an increasingly segregated

society, Sweden is now grappling with rising gang related crime and violence. In response to this issue, the country has gradually tightened legislation and expanded police authority, shifting towards a more authoritarian stance to restore order. The gradual crumbling of the welfare state, failure to accommodate immigrant populations and persistent segregation have thus been leading to societal and political tensions.

The deep roots of the social contract in **Türkiye** are directly related with its Ottoman past. The Ottomans did not engage in overseas colonisation like many European powers. However, the interactions and internal dynamics within the Ottoman Empire reveal a complex picture, with elements of a specific Ottoman colonialism. The Ottoman Empire's attitude as a contracting empire, trying to survive against expanding European powers, espoused the empire's defensive imperialist stance. The Ottoman Empire aimed at administrative centralisation and integrated its provinces into its political system. The Ottoman state was more concerned with internal control and consolidation, rather than the overseas colonial expansion characteristic of imperial practices of differentiation. Therefore, the Ottoman Empire did not have colonies, and its African policies expressed a sort of 'borrowed' colonialism. The enduring influence of the Ottoman Empire on Turkish politics is a key factor in understanding the roots of authoritarianism in the country. Despite Türkiye's formal democratisation following WWII, the military has since intervened in politics multiple times, complicating the country's democratic trajectory. The formation of the republic and the drivers of nation-building focused on a Turkish-Muslim identity, which often ended up excluding non-Muslim minorities. This process included Turkification policies that sought to unify the population through a common language and religion. The Turkish political culture can be defined through continuity rather than change, with the tradition of a powerful centralised state, the prominent role of the military and the absence of a robust civil society producing policies with a strong state.

The social contract in **Ukraine** is deeply rooted in the historical experience of being under the rule of empires: Russian, Austro-Hungarian and partly Ottoman. The conditions of Ukrainian territories within these states shaped a particular political culture, system of legal relations and idea of the citizens' role in society. This historical experience has led to the asymmetric development of a political culture in different regions of the country, while creating structural inequalities in state-society relations. The colonial subordination of the territory of Ukraine to various empires, and later to Soviet totalitarianism, led to the entrenchment of a paternalistic model of relations between citizens and the state. The Russian Empire, and later the Soviet Union, reproduced a model in which citizens were perceived as objects of state control rather than subjects. In such a system, state power was not seen as serving the public good, but as a bearer of power for its own sake. The situation was quite different in the parts of Ukraine that were under the rule of the Austro-Hungarian Empire. In the former model, the state was

perceived as an all-powerful guardian and civic participation was considered secondary or even dangerous. This is linked to late low levels of political culture, alienation from institutions and weak political subjectivity among citizens. All these historical experiences are also linked with low trust in state institutions, such as the parliament, courts, the police and executive authorities. Also, the inertia of post-Soviet power structures was also extremely strong. Furthermore, democratisation efforts were first accompanied by elites attempting to maintain their privileges and influence. However, after gaining independence in 1991 Ukraine did enter a new era of political and institutional development, but it did so with an authoritarian and paternalistic model of state governance inherited from the Soviet system. The Orange Revolution (2004) and the Revolution of Dignity (2013-2014) manifested public dissatisfaction with authoritarianism and corruption. These movements marked a paradigm shift in the relation between the state and society, representing a new type of civic mobilisation.

The previous overview of the country-cases involved in this research provides some examples of commonalities and divergences in the historical pathways of these countries. The next table offers a synthetic summary of the deep roots of each country's social contract, the main events and historical periods of these roots, and the most important current expressions of inequality which they express.

Countries	Deep roots	Main events-periods	Current inequalities
Bosnia-Herzegovina	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Territory was repeatedly annexed as part of different imperialist endeavours. • Nationalism shaped in Austro-Hungarian rule and reinforced within Yugoslavia. • Nazi occupation during WWII. • New forms of imperialism and external interference are shaping social contract. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ottoman empire (mid-15th to late-19th centuries). • Austro-Hungarian empire (up to WWI). • Nazi occupation (during WWII). • Kingdom (first) and Republic of (second) Yugoslavia (end 1992). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiethnic and multireligious nation, with concomitant intergroup tensions. • Political and ethnic tensions, as well as calls for secession (Republica Srpska).
Bulgaria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Independence came only after centuries of Ottoman rule (in 1908). • Post-independence state includes a large Turkish ethnic minority. • Authoritarian turn solidified in the 1930s, after violent coups and popular revolts. • Soviet colonisation post-WWII and move from totalitarian to authoritarian regime. • Fall of communist regime (1989) meant move towards Europe and liberalisation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Five centuries of Ottoman rule (ending only in 1908). • Rising authoritarianism (1930s), and close to Nazi regime (WWII). • Soviet totalitarianism (1947-54), and authoritarianism (end 1989). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A sizable Turkish ethnic minority after independence from Ottoman rule. • Ethnic Turks some representativeness after communism. Roma excluded. • Economic liberalisation following from the end of the communist regime.
Croatia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A part of Hungarian Kingdom, Habsburg Monarchy and Austro-Hungarian empire. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long Hungarian rule and Austro-Hungarian empire (till early XX). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political and ethnic tensions fuelled a war towards independence (1990s).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-lasting tensions between Croats and minorities (especially Serbs). • Incorporation into Kingdom of Yugoslavia of Kingdom of Serbs, Croats & Slovenes. • Short-lived independence following help from Nazi regime during WWII. • A part of communist Yugoslavia. Tension across ethnic groups after independence. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kingdom of Yugoslavia (interwar period). • Independent state with Nazi help during most of WWII. • Communist Yugoslavia between 1945 and 1991. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-lasting tensions between Croats and minorities (especially Serbs). • Recent efforts towards the inclusion of ethnic minorities, especially the Serbs.
Finland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constant imperial struggles with powerful neighbours: Russia and Sweden. • Resistance to Russian rule alongside an internal push towards democratisation. • Despite periods of turmoil, parliamentary democratic stability was always upheld. • Internal colonialism towards Sami people. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Swedish rule (from Middle Ages to 1809). • Russian rule (between 1809 and 1917). • Civil War (1918-1919), and after period of greater stability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legacy of imperial rule is still visible in legislative, institutional frameworks. • Legacy of imperial rule also still visible in linguistic and cultural landscapes. • Military culture has played a crucial role in shaping national discourse as well.
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tradition of centralised and authoritarian governance even after the revolution. • Revolutionary ideals of fraternity, equality and liberty as national foundations. • Vast colonial empire based on a civilising doctrine. Colonial authoritarianism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Absolutist ruling pre-Revolution. • Revolution, Napoleon, Empires (from 1789 to WWII). • Vichy regime, collaboration with Nazi regime (WWII). • Fifth Republic (1958 onwards). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colonial legacy still divisive and ignites struggles of identity, equity, belonging. • A continuing tradition of centralisation, uneasy with its revolutionary ideals. • Military and economic presence in Africa evokes fears of neocolonialism.

<p>Germany</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unification of Germany based on imperial authoritarian state, with a strong military. • Short albeit violent imperial colonial rule. • Nazi rule, including a radical expansionist policy rooted in racial ideology. • Partial sovereignty, European integration and reception of the past after WWII. • Reunification of East and West Germany. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prussian dominance, unification, segway to empire (18th-19th). • Late German colonial, imperial rule (late-19th until WWI). • Nazi rule (1933-1945). • East and West (1945-1990). • Reunification days (post-1990). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reunification added decisive layers of inequality to country's social fabric. • Reception of past still important part of memory and identity (and inequalities). • Political culture remains influenced by country's authoritarian past.
<p>Hungary</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kingdom of Hungary and its allegiance to Western Christianity. • Long foreign dominance under Ottoman rule and the Habsburg Monarchy. • Post WWI fragmentation, which led to Soviet-style authoritarian rule. • Soviet rule, and tight sphere of influence, after WWII. • Western integration and late experiences of electoral autocracy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kingdom of Hungary (11-16th). • Ottoman empire, Habsburg rule, Austro-Hungarian (1526-1918). • Interwar authoritarianism. • Soviet influence and rule (1945-1989). • Westernization and late electoral autocracy (1990s and after). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Territorial inequalities, divide between capital city and rest of the country. • Ethnic diversity is fraught issue as well as inequalities across gender.
<p>Portugal</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early state formation, with strong support from, and ties to, the Catholic church. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-colonial state period (pre-15th century). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colonial efforts as a source of lingering developmental problems.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-lasting Portuguese colonial empire, as source of national building, identity. • Authoritarian regime as a colonial regime too. Simultaneous end of both regimes. • Democratisation with a revolutionary and radical imprint, under military tutelage. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colonial empire (until 1974), and Estado Novo (1933-1974). • Democratisation, decolonization & Europeanization (post-1974). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inequalities faced by colonial subjects generated distinct immigration flows.
Sweden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional power during the imperial period through state unions and occupations. • Experience of overseas colonialism was limited in its extension and duration. • Early democratization, as a constitutional democracy; legacy of freedom of press. • Cultural and religious assimilation forced on Sámi; racialization of minorities. • Unsuccessful migrant integration policies, which led to high residential segregation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Swedish empire (1611-1721). • Short periods of colonial intents overseas (1638-63/1784-1878). • Democratisation (with universal suffrage instituted in 1921). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industrial growth absorbed immigrants from several regions. • Decline of welfare state, segregation, and failure to accommodate migrants. • Recent increases in gang violence are driving a rise in law-and-order policies.
Türkiye	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ottoman empire, which did not engage in overseas colonialism. • Defensive orientation towards European nations and other imperial powers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ottoman empire (from late 13th to early 20th century). • Democratisation (after WWII). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong Turkish-Muslim identity, which leads to exclusion of non-Muslims. • Lingering tradition of centralised state, strong military and a weak civil society.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centralised administrative processes and imperial practices of differentiation. • Post-imperial nation-building based on a Turkification and Turkish-Muslim identity. 		
Ukraine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience of being under rule of empires -- Russian, Austro-Hungarian, Ottoman. • Regional asymmetries in political culture, and inequalities in state-society relations. • Soviet regime led to inertia of post-Soviet institutions and centralised structures. • Paternalistic relations between state and citizens; civic participation discouraged. • New phase of civic mobilisation, including volunteering (partly related to the War). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Austro-Hungarian, Russian, and Ottoman empires (pre-WWI). • Incorporation into Soviet Union (1922-1991). • Independence, democratisation (after 1991). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lingering Russian and Soviet legacy of citizens perceived as objects of state. • Also lingering structural inequalities in state-society relations across regions. • Low levels of trust in state institutions. • Paradigm shift in recent years, with a growing culture of civic mobilisation.

Cross-fertilising analysis of the deep roots of European Social Contracts

This report provides a comprehensive overview of the impact and legacy of empires and authoritarian regimes on European Social Contracts. Through a diachronic perspective, major political, economic and social shifts in eleven country-cases are identified. The aim is twofold: reviewing the historical evolution of the countries' social contracts and elucidating how those historical transformations impact their current underpinnings and respective inequalities. The prism of analysis pursued here envisages widening scales for interpretation. Moving beyond an internal perspective, the cross-reading of the country sections reveals the value of including transnational dynamics, especially in multi-ethnic, multiracial, multireligious and multilingual societies. These societies' historical constitutions are contingent upon important imperial, colonial and authoritarian experiences.

Long view over the social contracts

While social contract theories do not explain how social arrangements historically emerged (D2.1, p. 11), this report provides an overview of the historical processes that led to — or interfered with — the formation of national social agreements. In this regard, it aims to contribute to enriching those theories. The country reports presented below are formulated as historical narratives. They were drafted by multidisciplinary teams who selected and interpreted the historical events and processes they considered most relevant in their respective countries, guided by the project's framework of the 'continuous construction of social contracts'. The interpretative line proposed was drawn retrospectively, tracing developments from an indeterminate past to the present configuration of 11 states/nations/societies.

The compilation of the country-case contributions teases out several important points for the continuing empirical and theoretical work of the project. These include the implications of methodological nationalism; the contemporaneous shaping of states and political philosophy; the materialisation of social contracts; the rise of nationalism; and profound social and historical transformations, such as industrialisation and technological development. While these dimensions manifest in various ways across the cases, they also mark out possibilities of how to address them within and between contexts. With this initial reading, it is possible to set the stage for the exploration of the theoretical and empirical approaches to social contracts

pursued in the project. The problem of methodological nationalism, for example, is an issue for any country-case approach to empirics in future research; at the same time, the perspective of recent crises both transcends, and falls back to, the national contexts and perspectives. Therefore, the report alludes to the continuous interplay between national contexts and territorial settings.

A cross-reading of the country reports

The report addresses the potential implications of methodological nationalism. As previously noted, “the assumption that the proper territorial unit for social contracts is the national one” is a core element of social contract theories, from Hobbes to the post-Rawlsian literature (D2.1, p. 31). To mitigate potential biases arising from analysing the evolution of social contracts through national case studies, a cross-reading of the country reports is conducted. This approach enables the identification of common vectors across cases. Rather than focusing on national scales, this also offers insights into the occurrence of similar processes across different political entities in overlapping time periods. It does not pursue strict comparability, nor a reading of historical developments based on rigid time scales. Such an exercise would risk oversimplifying complex historical trajectories. Instead, the objective is to identify enduring patterns and long-term dynamics that transcend both temporal and national boundaries.

For the eleven cases examined, key historical events that have contributed to the ongoing construction of social contracts are highlighted. These events date back to periods preceding the emergence of the territories involved in this study as independent countries, or even their establishment as nation-states. On the one hand, the reports, which are presented in an expanded version below and have been summarized in the previous section, emphasize how the continuous processes framing social contracts were influenced by the creation or (re-)establishment of federal and nation-states, the (re)configuration of national and international borders following the dissolution of empires and federal states, as well as international conflicts and civil wars. On the other hand, the reports offer an overview of how the political philosophies of modern European nation-states were forged by concrete political and social contexts in different countries. Although this task does not allow a macro-historical analysis, some long-term trends can be identified and the object of further inquiry. Notably, this will include T3.4 on European borders and colonialism, which examines the impacts and inequalities generated by imperialism and colonialism.

The ‘long 19th century’ was a period of profound transformation, setting the stage for the materialization of social contract ideals that had been theorized in earlier centuries (see D2.1). In many cases, the driving force behind these changes were revolutions and (civil) wars. This process began with the Fall of the Bastille in 1789, marking the transition from the Ancient

Regime to Liberalism. However, this process was not linear. In France, for example, the trajectory was interrupted by the Reign of Terror, the First Napoleonic Empire, and the restrictive Second Empire under Napoleon III. Other countries experienced similar cycles of advances and setbacks. In Portugal, for instance, the Liberal Revolution of 1820 was reversed by the restoration of Absolutism three years later, a setback only overcome by the outcome of the Liberal Wars (1828–1834), which ultimately led to the consolidation of the Constitutional Monarchy.

One should highlight the rise of nationalism throughout the nineteenth century as another driving force for changing and consolidating social contracts. This is true, even when framed within imperial structures, as seen through the German Unification and the strengthening of Balkan nationalism within the Austro-Hungarian Empire. These dynamics played out across the territories under study. They occurred mostly in isolation or conditioned by larger dynamics of power, such as the Russo-Turkish War, which led to the independence of Bulgaria and Romania. Rivalries between Empires led to attempts towards the creation of nations. This strategy of weakening imperial powers was shown for instance through the pressure exerted on Ottoman lands in the nineteenth century by British, Russian, French and Austro-Hungarian Empires (Burbank and Cooper, 2010). The 'long 19th century' culminated with the outbreak of World War I. This conflict, originally between European powers, became a global war due to their imperial configurations, leading to the collapse of several ancient empires and sparking a second wave of the emergence of nation-states in Europe. The revolutions of 1848 (a year often called the 'Spring of Nations') had been pivotal in fostering the rise of nationalism and sparking uprisings whose reverberations were felt throughout Europe for decades to come. However, as the history of Central Europe following the two world wars and the contemporary history of the Balkans shows, societies paid a huge price trying to match the boundaries of nations with those of states. This ended up leading to great losses in terms of human lives, territory and economic power.

Other major transformations in the nineteenth century were driven by the economic and social changes brought about by industrialization, international trade, and economic development. The expansion of European overseas empires across Africa and Asia significantly contributed to reforms and shifts at various levels of society. In fact, the expansion of the overseas empires of several European powers led to the strengthening of the state in England and France, in the late seventeenth and eighteenth centuries (Burbank & Cooper, 2010, p. 8). A similar process occurred in Portugal, as argued previously.

A key aspect to consider is how certain conceptions became enduring and foundational pillars of the social contract, resisting political and social changes over time. One notable example is France, where Republican ideals (rooted in the revolutionary principles of liberty, equality, and fraternity), namely secularism or *laïcité*, became deeply embedded in the foundational matrix of the modern state, the country's social contract and its national identity, and resisted changes in political regimes, from the French Revolution to the Fifth Republic.

Empires, nationalism and irredentism

While this report does not aim to analyse competing imperial models, it does highlight how social contracts evolved within multinational and multiethnic empires in ways similar to those of nation-states. Despite their differences, empires as well as nation-states seek that people be ruled by their institutions, even if coercive means are needed (Burbank & Cooper, 2010, p. 8). The forging of a sense of community can be pivotal for imperial/state-building processes, although it creates some exclusions, and thus affect the social contract and social cohesion. The nation-state often treats people inside its border as a homogenous group, leading to the exclusion of those who do not belong. While Empires are per definition spaces that integrate different peoples, this is often achieved at the expense of coercion, hierarchy and the ability to apply and manage distinct systems of laws and governance within the imperial structure, in what can be designated as 'politics of difference' (*ibid.*). Nevertheless, Empires can also seek to homogenize different populations that live within their boundaries, especially when they rely on the support given by local and imperial elites for that purpose. One could mention how Ottoman bureaucratic elites resorted to developing 'Ottomanism', conceptualized as a "means to create bonds of social solidarity that could transcend religious or ethnic differences" among the subjects of the Empire (Roudometof, 1999, p. 238). Although it lacked strong popular support, Yugoslavism can be listed as a similar mechanism, having been essentially an intellectual movement promoted by some Habsburg Serbs and the Croatian intelligentsia, during the 19th century (*ibid.*, p. 237).

This overview also sheds light on the role played by imperialism and the political usage of the past in boosting nationalism, leading to the emergence and consolidation of nation-states between the mid-19th century and the first quarter of the 20th century. German history includes different imperialisms (imposed internally and externally), offering inward and outward perspectives on the dynamics between imperialism(s) and changes in the social contract. Since German unification, nationalism has also played a crucial role in overcoming traditional regional forms of identification, while conjuring images of the 'enemy' became the primary means for constructing a German national identity. After the expansionism of the totalitarian Nazi regime and its defeat in WWII, the country found itself occupied by foreign powers (US, Russia, United Kingdom and France), which divided it and turned it into a Cold War battlefield.

The Western and Soviet Imperialisms in Germany, surveilling the Federal Republic of Germany and the German Democratic Republic, would end only after the fall of the Berlin Wall. This event paved the way for German reunification in the 1990s and the recovery of its full sovereignty. Another case relates to the (re)emergence of nation-states in Eastern Europe (namely in Bulgaria, Croatia and Bosnia-Herzegovina), after the end of the Ottoman rule in the 19th century. Afterwards, and under Austro-Hungarian rule, Bosnian and Croatian nationalism developed significantly. Likewise, Portugal also showcases how the imperialisation of the nation was forged as a process aimed at boosting national identity and legitimising different political regimes.

European overseas colonialism fundamentally reshaped demographics, economies and power structures through colonial relations, with lasting consequences for European Social Contracts. The exploitation of colonies in Africa, Asia, the Americas and Northern Europe enriched European economies, fuelling industrialisation and the expansion of the welfare state, while also embedding racial and economic hierarchies that persist across Europe. France and Portugal represent the two major instances of this among the CO3 countries, but other countries also had a role in overseas colonialism, with Sweden as an example. The 1884-85 Berlin Conference, formalising the division of Africa among European powers, exemplified the imperial mindset of Europe as a continent, rather than distinct empires acting alone. It dictated colonial governance and influenced domestic policies, reinforcing authoritarian rule and exclusionary nationalism within Europe. The wealth extracted from colonies financed social programs and infrastructure in imperial metropolises, creating disparities in development and contributing to modern debates over reparations and migration. Moreover, industrialisation came at huge human costs, through the international slave trade and the epistemological annihilation of colonised cultures.

The cross-reading of the eleven country cases facilitates a historical understanding of the emergence of irredentist claims and movements across different territories and historical periods (see the cases of Bulgaria and Hungary, for instance). The country reports of Bulgaria, Croatia, Hungary, and Ukraine trace the evolution of medieval kingdoms and political entities that lost their independence with the rise of the Modern era and the consolidation of continental empires (Habsburg, Russian and Ottoman). Centuries later, these historical events fuelled “myths of ancient statehood”, framed by political actors and movements to legitimate irredentist claims (Nagle, 2025). This report pays attention to contemporary dynamics, such as a kind of irredentist nation-state building associated with the re-establishment of Bulgarian state in the late nineteenth century, which continued to shape national identity in the subsequent decades (see p. 44). A similar approach was followed by the newly formed nation states of the Balkans. The role played by Greek, Serb and Bulgarian nationalist intelligentsia,

between 1830 and 1880, has been noted in that it produced romantic versions of the 'nation' and national narratives that generated irredentist dreams that would afterwards lead to rivalries between the Balkans' states (Roudometof, 1999, p. 240).

This work also addresses how the loss of two-thirds of Hungarian territory, resulting from the Treaty of Trianon (1921) after World War I, generated 'national traumas', played an important role in forging Hungarian national identity and, more recently, has become a "driving force behind contemporary right-wing populist politics" in the country (p. 83). Other cases, such as the Croatian Republic of Herzeg-Bosnia, involving Croatia and Bosnia-Herzegovina may be object of inquiry by another project tasks, in case irredentist frames are analyzed.

Additionally, it explores the uses of the past in today's politics and international affairs, by eliciting cases of irredentist endeavours. A prominent example is the rhetoric used by President Vladimir Putin to justify Russia Federation's annexation of Crimea in 2014 and, more recently, the full-scale invasion of Ukraine in 2022. This rhetoric is largely sustained in irredentist claims. According to Nagle, these irredentist frames resort to three framing devices: "a myth of ancient statehood"; "sacred people, causes and lands"; and "the national family" (2025, p. 4-9).

Last remarks: key features of the social contract in perspective

Another key feature of the social contract is its adaptability; in the sense that it can be manageable regardless of the political regime. The report highlights the emergence of authoritarian regimes in the interwar period and their capacity to shape the social contract in the way that best serves their interests. These regimes typically effectively manage the social contract by manipulating information and propaganda, fostering the ideological inculcation of the populations, instilling fear through surveillance and political policing, and by using various tools for oppression and control. Such mechanisms change the living conditions of populations, and their impacts extend well beyond the fall of these regimes.

A further trend identified in the report is the correlation between involvement in large-scale conflicts and their outcome, and the survival of empires and political regimes. World War I led to the collapse of long-standing empires, such as the Austro-Hungarian, Ottoman, and Russian empires, as well as Imperial Germany. The aftermath of World War II also had a profound impact on Europe's totalitarian regimes, shaping both their survival and global geopolitics. While Nazism and Italian Fascism collapsed, Stalinism endured, and the post-war international order favoured the rise of authoritarian regimes aligned with the Soviet Bloc in East Germany and Eastern Europe. These regimes persisted throughout the Cold War, only collapsing with the fall of the Berlin Wall and the revolutions of 1989 and the early 1990s.

Finally, this historical glance offers a diachronic perspective on how societies have navigated crises, upheavals, and revolutions, often leading to substantial alterations or the reinforcement of the social contract. It demonstrates the capacity of the social contract to adapt to different crises and contexts. This aligns with the core concept of the ‘continuous dimension’ positioned in the CO3 model, which refers to the social contract’s ability to remain “open to renegotiation based on the recognition of overlooked interests and new challenges” (D2.1, p. 98). The report also emphasizes that the ‘resilience’ of social contracts — another key dimension of the CO3 theoretical model (D2.3) — should not be seen as a recent phenomenon, but as the result of a historical continuum. It involves the intersection of specific economic, political, and social circumstances with broader historical processes, which are in turn influenced by local, regional, and (trans-/inter-) national dynamics. By providing this long-term perspective, the report advances one of the CO3 project’s key challenges: developing a social contract theory that is both democratic and open to change.

Current inequalities

After WWII, and while decolonisation unfolded, colonial powers such as France and Portugal engaged in multiple colonial wars to deter the independence of their colonies. During the post-war period, to consolidate its presence in Africa and prevent winds of liberation, Portugal implemented policies of white settlement in Angola and Mozambique, generating waves of migration from the metropole. The decolonisation process generated massive waves of migration (either of white, or of local racially minoritized populations) from former colonies to European countries. France and Portugal still grapple with their colonial pasts in relation to migrant communities, while the former Austro-Hungarian and Ottoman territories deal with the fragmentation of imperial legacies. Nationalism has been a dominant force in Eastern Europe, where the collapse of the Soviet Union led to the (re-)emergence of nation-states. The tension between civic nationalism and irredentism – claims to “lost territories” – remains relevant in countries such as Hungary and Ukraine. In contrast, Western Europe has largely embraced supranational governance through the EU, though nationalist movements seem to recently be challenging this trend.

Other post-colonial migrations to Europe were also sustained and promoted as a solution to the shortage of labour in some economic sectors of some countries. The search for better living conditions, and the prevalence of temporary guestworker programs in many Western European countries torn by WWII, also fuelled migrations within Europe, from the postwar period to the present. These movements occurred in several directions, typically taking place from peripheral and semi-peripheral countries in the European context, and Europe’s Eastern and Southern neighbourhood(s). Just to mention some of the most relevant, there have been

migrations: from Southern and Eastern European countries and the former Yugoslavia to Central and Northern Europe; across borders, such as the Finnish going to Sweden after WWII; or from Türkiye to Germany (and other European countries, such as the Netherlands).

Furthermore, as decolonisation progressed, former colonial powers reengineered colonialism in new forms that contributed to political instability and authoritarian rule. This also generated waves of migration from former colonies, with these migrants currently being considered a threat to European cultures and national identities. Europe's imperialist legacy remains embedded in contemporary debates over race, immigration, reparations and former colonial powers' responsibilities to address inequalities.

The treatment of indigenous and minority groups remains deeply rooted in the colonialism of European Social Contracts. For instance, Sámi are the last transnational indigenous people of Europe, with its territory (Sápmi) colonised by Norway, Sweden, Finland and Russia. This case shows how European colonialism expanded from the centre in all directions, not exclusively towards the South. The Roma, Jewish and Muslim populations of many countries have faced systemic discrimination across Europe. Muslims remained in the Iberian Peninsula, the Balkans and Eastern Europe after the defeat of Muslim establishments and the end of the Ottoman Empire in those territories. The persistence of anti-Semitism, Islamophobia, the marginalisation of Roma populations, and debates over Indigenous rights highlight these groups' enduring struggle for inclusive governance. The recognition of minority rights has been uneven across Europe. While EU policies overall attempt to promote inclusivity, national governments vary substantially in their implementation. Legal protections for minorities, whether ethnic, linguistic or religious, often emerge from historical struggles rather than from proactive governance. The consolidation of these rights remains a crucial feature of modern European democracy.

Soviet-era domination functioned as a form of foreign authoritarianism or colonialism in Eastern Europe, deeply shaping political and economic structures. However, scholars are divided on the conceptualisation of the domination of this historical power, as well as on its varying effects in different countries. Bosnia-Herzegovina, Croatia (during the Yugoslavian period), Bulgaria, East Germany (German Democratic Republic), Hungary and Finland were subjected to Soviet influence, which affected their trajectories of democratisation and economic development. The collapse of the Soviet Union left a vacuum that former satellite states have navigated with varying degrees of success, with some embracing EU integration and others leaning towards nationalist or authoritarian rule, and some even going through what appears a hybrid pathway, entailing both processes.

The impact of the two World Wars, and more recently, of the so-called Balkan Wars and the Russian invasion of Ukraine, have reshaped, and are still reshaping, national borders, governance models and social cohesion. The devastation created by these, and other, wars has accelerated the decline of empires and fuelled nationalist movements, particularly in Eastern Europe. The post-WWII period saw the consolidation of democratic institutions in Western Europe, whereas Eastern European nations often fell under Soviet influence, delaying their democratisation. The deep roots of the social contract also contain the regional disparities that remain a defining characteristic of European politics. Moreover, rural areas, often more conservative and economically marginalised, contrast sharply with urban centres, which tend to be hubs of progressive politics and economic growth. This divide fuels nationalist rhetoric, resistance to EU policies and debates over economic redistribution.

Religion also remains a powerful force shaping societal norms and governance structures. Catholicism, Orthodox Christianity, Protestantism and Islamism have historically played distinct roles in shaping national identities and legal frameworks. For example, Portugal and Croatia retain strong Catholic influences, while Orthodox Christianity is deeply embedded in Bulgaria and Ukraine. In Türkiye, the legacy of secularism under Atatürk is increasingly being challenged by Islamic conservatism. While religious institutions no longer wield absolute political power, they continue to influence debates on social issues and inequalities, including those related to gender and (ethno-racial) minority rights.

Particularly, the struggle for gender rights can also be mentioned as an important element, reflecting broader shifts in the social contract. Women's suffrage was achieved in different moments across Europe. Yet, conservative and anti-gender movements, often grounded in nationalistic rhetoric rather than a deep religious commitment, continue to challenge gender equality policies. These movements exploit anxieties over social change, positioning themselves against EU-led human rights initiatives.

By looking within Europe, it is evident that the historical legacies of imperialism, colonialism and authoritarianism continue to shape the contemporary social contract. The persistence of these legacies influences national politics, governance structures and societal cohesion across Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Portugal, Sweden, Türkiye, Ukraine, and the EU. The origins of modern nation-states are often entangled with external domination (as in the case of Eastern European countries) or inter-state rivalry (especially in Western Europe). For example, France and Germany emerged as centralised powers through internal consolidation, but also external conflicts; Portugal often disputed its national sovereignty against attempted conquests by Spain; and Bulgaria, Hungary and Ukraine have histories marked by foreign rule, be it Ottoman, Habsburg, Soviet

or Russian. The long shadow of external rule influences contemporary political sovereignty and public perceptions on state legitimacy.

Final remarks

The deep roots of the social contract in Europe illustrate how historical legacies shape contemporary governance and political identities. National policies, regional tensions, social cohesion and foreign relations continue to be influenced by the interwoven histories of imperialism, colonialism and authoritarian rule, as well as their relation to war and different kinds of national and international crises. Multi-sectorial development agreements between former colonising and colonised countries are shaped by this common colonial past, being perceived in many cases as forms of neocolonialism. A visible facet of this enduring history pertains to France's interventions in Africa, such as its military presence in Mali; another example refers to European companies operating in Africa, extracting mineral and oil resources, or building critical infrastructure. Additionally, The European Green Deal, through which the EU set the path to implement a green transition, with the aim of reaching climate neutrality by 2050, has been increasingly criticised for its neocolonial conceptions. This is used as the discursive strategy leveraged by the EU, encompassing the establishment of multiple 'green new deals' with third countries. The purpose is to convert ecological crises into profitable opportunities, by portraying the EU as a leading force – i.e., a normative power – in the green transition. This image of combatting climate change masks the inherent purpose of allowing the EU to omit its historical responsibilities in global environmental disasters, while guaranteeing its economic and political leadership, as well as favourable access conditions to raw materials (Almeida et al., 2023).

As Europe navigates challenges such as nationalism, refugees, climate change, ecological sustainability, democratic backsliding, and social inequalities, understanding these deep-rooted legacies is essential for fostering resilient social contracts. Furthermore, this understanding should also allow for envisioning more inclusionary collective imaginaries and European societies.

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Expanded overview of the deep roots of the social contract in CO3 countries

Bosnia-Herzegovina

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Overview

Bosnia-Herzegovina became an independent state in 1992 due to the breakup of Yugoslavia. Independence brought about a complex political, economic, institutional and identity-related transition process that was pivotal to the reconstitution of the country's social contract. Notwithstanding, the social contract articulated in this process was shaped by longer-term processes associated with its imperial past. As argued by Malesevic (2021), Bosnian nationalism developed significantly under Austro-Hungarian rule and was further reinforced within Yugoslavia. Thus, the strategic relevance of the Socialist Republic of Bosnia and Herzegovina within the Federation allowed for peaceful development during this period (*ibid.*).

The deep roots of Bosnia-Herzegovina as a political entity can be traced back to the 12th century with the establishment of the Bosnian Banate, a *de facto* independent medieval state for most of its existence, that evolved into the Kingdom of Bosnia in the 14th century. This period was marked by religiopolitical quarrels and increasing autonomy from outside powers, such as Hungary and Byzantium, desiring control over the territory (Fine, 1994).

Starting from the mid-15th century, the Kingdom's territory was annexed as part of different imperial endeavours, including the Ottoman Empire (until the late 19th century) and the Austro-Hungarian Empire (until World War I). This imperial legacy implied profound changes in this territory's political and cultural landscape. The Ottomans introduced meaningful socio-political administrative changes, including the reorganisation of administrative units, a new landholding scheme and a class-religious social differentiation system. Overall, a process of Islamisation emerged, resulting in the conversion of Orthodox people and a significant number of Catholics fleeing Bosnia (Velikonja, 2003). Due to the frequency of Ottoman wars with European powers and epidemics, as well as forced and economic migrations, considerable socio-demographic changes occurred. A Slavic-speaking Muslim community emerged as the largest ethno-religious group in the territory.

Still, multi-ethnicity and multi-religiosity unfolded in an environment of overall tolerance, respect and peace. Violent confrontations between Muslim landlords and Christian peasants occurred in the mid-19th century, but these were mostly motivated by socio-economic issues, rather than by religious or ethnic grievances (Belloni & Ramović, 2019). The Ottoman imperial rule was not without resistance, including revolts within Bosnia, which were contained by the Empire's military and others benefitting from the status quo (aristocrats and local political elites). This paved the way for the emergence of nationalist movements in Bosnia in the mid-19th century, highly influenced by Serbian and Croatian nationalism (Malcolm, 2002).

Following the 1878 Congress of Berlin, Bosnia-Herzegovina was annexed into the Austro-Hungarian Empire, under whose rule it remained until World War I (WWI). Several social, economic and administrative reforms were implemented with the creation of new political institutions and the establishment of industries. These reforms also attempted to dissipate South Slav nationalism, by encouraging the recognition of a Bosnian identity along with an anti-Serb repression policy (Banac, 1988, Hajdarpasic, 2015).

After WWI, Bosnia-Herzegovina was integrated into the Kingdom of Yugoslavia. Two major trends emerged in the territory's political landscape at this point: socio-economic unrest over property redistribution and the formation of several political parties. During Nazi occupation, a severe extermination campaign of Serbs, Jews, Roma and dissidents was undertaken with profound consequences for the territory's collective memory. In 1941, Yugoslavian communists (led by Josip Broz Tito) organised a multi-ethnic resistance group that played a pivotal role in assuring that Bosnia-Herzegovina was reestablished as a republic within the Social Federal Republic of Yugoslavia after WWII (Redžić, 2005).

Under Tito's ruling, Bosnia's political situation was stable and prosperous – as in other parts of the Yugoslavian territory. The republic became the central base for the development of Yugoslavia's military defence industry, while employment rates were high and socio-economic rights were recognised for all citizens, including women. This allowed for the development of a strong Bosnian political elite, which was crucial to the protection of the Republic's sovereignty in the turbulent period following Tito's death in 1980 (Malcolm, 2002). Even more importantly, at a later stage, this political elite paved the way to Bosnia's independence (*ibid.*).

Political, social and economic inequalities

The political, social and economic consequences of this imperial past significantly impacted the constitution and development of Bosnia-Herzegovina's social contract after the country declared its independence in 1992. Moreover, Bosnia-Herzegovina's post-communist

transition was further constrained by the so-called Bosnian War (1992-1995). This war significantly impacted the country's ability to resume its path towards stability, equity and the fulfilment of the social contract's conditions to its multi-national and multi-ethnic population. The conflict was ended by the Dayton Peace Agreements, not without meaningful consequences for the current political configuration of the country. As a result, the peace implementation has been supervised by the High Representative for Bosnia and Herzegovina (HRBiH), selected by the Peace Implementation Council, which remains the highest political authority in the country. The HRBiH's mandate includes working with Bosnia-Herzegovina's people and institutions, as well as the international community, to ensure the country evolves into a peaceful and viable democracy for integration into Euro-Atlantic institutions (Office of the High Representative, 2025).

Within this framework, Bosnia-Herzegovina developed into a liberal parliamentary representative democracy. According to the Constitution (Annex 4 of the Dayton Agreements), the Presidency of the country comprises three members (one Bosnian, one Serb and one Croat) who collectively serve as the head of the state. Formally, the country is divided into two major entities (the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina and Republika Srpska), making it a consociational confederation, according to Bose (2003). The link between ethnicity and representation, established by the Dayton Agreements, has contributed to the strengthening of ethnic political elites and the consolidation of Bosnia-Herzegovina's political system as "an ethnocracy or an ethnically based kleptocracy" (Global State of Democracy Initiative, 2024). In fact, Belloni and Ramović (2019) contend the Dayton Agreements reinforced antagonistic political identities, fostering the *de facto* creation of two social contracts. The first is a hegemonic elite social contract that includes political elites from the main ethnic groups – Bosnians, Serbs and Croats. The second is an everyday social contract that involves ordinary citizens, struggling to cope with the country's challenging socio-economic status.

The Constitution of Bosnia-Herzegovina, as part of the Dayton Agreements, is an international contract, revealing a top-down approach to a renegotiation of the social contract with foreign actors. Rather than being an organic outcome, the social contract emerges, at least partially, as an external imposition on the people of Bosnia-Herzegovina. Despite protecting human rights and fundamental freedoms for all persons in the country without discrimination, the Constitution identifies Bosnians, Croats and Serbs as the constituent people of the country. This outcome has been seen as a contradiction and a form of discrimination against other Bosnian citizens, including Jews and Roma, as determined by the European Court of Human Rights in 2019 (Human Rights Watch, 2019).

The political system of post-independence Bosnia-Herzegovina has also been characterized by persistent and significant corruption. In addition, the High Representative is charged with

so-called Bonn powers, which grant veto power, as well as the ability to bypass and/or remove elected officials, which may be perceived as undemocratic (Human Rights Watch 2019). Also, the country's economic performance has been constrained by challenges associated with post-war reconstruction and economic liberalisation. The so-called Bosnian Spring in 2014 highlighted popular dissatisfaction with the perceived political inertia of ruling elites, high unemployment rates, economic stagnation, gender-based violence and discrimination, emigration and brain drain. There is also a perceived deterioration of women's rights compared to the socialist period, when women's employment and socio-economic rights were highly supported. In the post-independence period, a re-traditionalization of gender roles has emerged, resulting in the limitation of women's rights (Dobrotić & Obradović, 2020). For instance, recent childcare policies have transformed women's social citizenship, contributing to their marginalisation within the social contract (*ibid.*).

Notwithstanding, alternatives have been slowly emerging from non-nationalistic and inter-ethnic grassroots movements asking for a more resilient social contract in Bosnia-Herzegovina (Belloni & Ramović, 2019). More recently, political and ethnic tensions, including calls for secession from the Republica Srpska, have been rising, naturally granting legitimacy to fears of further Balkanisation in the region. Also, Bosnia-Herzegovina's complex transition cannot be dissociated from the development of relations with the European Union (EU). Despite several challenges relating to the rule of law, the EU's protection of minority rights in the country and public administration reforms have been an important part of reconstituting the country's social contract (Koneska, Huskic & Kraniqi, 2023; Bargués & Morillas, 2021). These relations have culminated with the granting of candidate status to Bosnia-Herzegovina in December 2022, and the starting of negotiations towards that objective in 2024.

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Bulgaria

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Overview

Bulgarian statehood has existed since the early Middle Ages. Historians accept 681 as the beginning of the Bulgarian state (Crampton, 2005). The ancient origins and long history of Bulgarian statehood, with three Bulgarian kingdoms (681-1018, 1185-1396 and 1878-1946) and the Republican period (socialist 1946-1989, then post-socialist since 1989), are a source of special pride for Bulgarians. There is also pride in the relatively early adoption of Orthodox Christianity (863) and the key role the Bulgarian state played in the adoption and spread of the Cyrillic alphabet (Daskalov & Mishkova, 2013). Another milestone of contemporary Bulgarian identity is the religious resistance to state authority by the socio-religious 'Bogomils' movement – spread across Europe through heretical religious movements of Cathars and Albigenses. Today, these events are among the drivers of national-populist voter mobilisation. This is well exemplified by the renaming of the official holiday of May 24 – this most cherished by Bulgarians holiday was previously known as the "Day of Bulgarian education and culture and the Slavic script." Prompted by their dwindling electoral support, the national populists from IMRO and the coalition United Patriots framed the national pride of Bulgarians as the nation that 'gave the world the Cyrillic alphabet', and in 2020, under conditions of mass anti-government protests (United Patriots were part of the ruling coalition) they managed to pass a name change through Parliament. The holiday is now celebrated as "May 24 - Day of the holy brothers Cyril and Methodius, the Bulgarian alphabet, education and culture and the Slavic letters," (BNR 2020).

In 1396, the Bulgarian state became part of the Ottoman Empire, ending the second Bulgarian kingdom. After almost five centuries under Ottoman rule, because of the Russo-Turkish war in 1877-1878, the Bulgarian state was reestablished – initially recognised as a tributary principality, then from 1908 as a sovereign independent state. The Provisional Russian Government in Bulgaria, headed by Count Dondukov, drew up an 'Organic statute' (as the draft of the new Constitution was originally called) for the new state (1879). Under these conditions – which may seem like a form of partial temporary colonisation by Russian imperial forces, which would presumably fortify the subservient status of the newly liberated state entity yet proved otherwise (Vinkovetsky, 2018) – the social contract in Bulgaria began to be established.

The re-established Bulgarian state included a sizable Turkish ethnic minority. Though formally providing equal rights to those of other ethnic groups, representatives of the formerly dominant ethnic group were not included in negotiations of the new nation's social contract. The Constituent Assembly adopted the Tarnovo Constitution of 1879, which exhibited two partly contradictory strands, corresponding to both nationalist and egalitarian-Rousseauian concerns (Smilov & Jileva, 2009). The first strove to rebuild the 'lost unity of the nation', while the latter aimed to create a commonwealth of free citizens, irrespective of their economic, ethnic or religious status, enjoying universal male suffrage. The Tarnovo Constitution, with its progressive, egalitarian notion of citizenship, became a symbol of the long-awaited freedom. This constitution opposed serfdom and slavery, part of the collective memory, considering the plight of Bulgarians under Ottoman rule. It was also thought to demonstrate the superiority of the free Bulgarian state to the Ottoman Empire (Lubenov & Stanev, 2020).

Over time, Bulgarian governments developed special regulations about managing the land, but also the religious, cultural and educational institutions connected to Muslim ethnic Turks. Changes in land tenure advanced a conception of national citizenship in which, despite individual (male) legal equality, Turkish Muslims and Bulgarian Christians carried out distinct roles as members of communities. In other words, the breakdown of late Ottoman land tenure supported the establishment of Bulgarian sovereignty and aided in generating some capital for Bulgarian industrialisation. But this process ultimately provoked ethno-religious antagonisms, encouraged rival Bulgarian and Turkish nationalisms, as well as the political marginalisation of Turkish Muslims (Markova 2017, p. 24). Thus, of the two strands of the Constitution identified above, the commitment to build a nation-state by restoring the imagined 'national unity' prevailed (Smilov & Jileva, 2009). This commitment unduly determined the course of Bulgarian politics for the better part of the following century (*ibid.*). The main consensus that emerged was ethno-nationalistic in character. The most lasting narrative constructed by the new state was the 'unification of all ethnic Bulgarians within one state' (Ilchev, 1996) which included parts of the Ottoman Empire, Greece and Serbia. A similar approach was followed by most newly formed nation states in the Balkans. Balkan politicians, intellectuals and nationalist organisations legitimised nation-building projects by "manipulat[ing] symbolic boundaries in order to produce collective redefinition of parts of the Ottoman Empire as 'unredeemed' territories" (Roudometof, 2000). This kind of irredentist nation-state building helped define Muslims in Bulgaria as a distinct Turkish national minority or as Bulgarian Muslims poised for assimilation. Land also symbolised the resources of the imperial past, over which Turkish Muslims and Bulgarian Christians competed, as statesmen devised policies for economic modernisation (Roudometof, 2000).

The double catastrophe of the Balkan Wars and WWI crushed the illusion of restoring national unity and ushered in a turbulent period (Daskalov, 2005). Popular revolts were followed by violent coups, and finally, the abolition of the political parties (1934) solidified the authoritarian turn of the Bulgarian state. In this turbulent period preceding WWII, the authoritarian regime of King Boris III gained legitimacy because it projected stability onto the Bulgarian citizenry. Through diplomacy, Boris managed to regain some of the Bulgarian lands lost in the wars, but most of the territories perceived by Bulgaria as originally belonging to it remained outside the state. The accumulated disappointment of the lost wars encouraged irredentism, leading to a rapprochement between Bulgaria and Nazi Germany on the eve of WWII (Kalinova & Baeva, 2011). Although Bulgaria did not fight on Hitler's side, it received Yugoslav and Greek territories, which it administered after Nazi Germany invaded the region. Bulgaria thus enjoyed a colonialist status, occupying 40,000 square kilometres of land from neighbouring states, if only for a short period (1941-1944). Bulgarians take pride in saving Bulgarian Jews during WWII – 50,000 Jews from the 'old territory' were not sent to Nazi death camps, though some were still sent to labour camps in Bulgaria (Avramov, 2012). However, the Bulgarian administration of these newly occupied territories sent over 11,000 Jews to Nazi death camps (*ibid.*).

In early September 1944, the Soviet army occupied Bulgaria, and after WWII, a communist regime was gradually installed in the country. Constant communist-sponsored violence characterised the establishment of the communist rule, including killing a significant part of the national elite without trial or conviction; furthermore, 2,700 death sentences were issued under staged 'People's Tribunals' (Vezenkov, 2014). Under these conditions, the monarchy was abolished, and a new 'people's republican' constitution was adopted, following the presence of the Russian army on Bulgarian territory (Vezenkov, 2014). Its constant interference in the political process and the structuring of the state in this period (September 1944-1947) can be seen as a form of Soviet colonisation (Tlostanova, 2012). Inspired by the ideological model of the Soviet colonisers, the new 'republican' constitution was not negotiated, but rather unanimously adopted in December 1947, after the anti-communist opposition was marginalised and its leader, Nikola Petkov, was arrested and sentenced to death.

Over the following years, the communist regime was consolidated under conditions of a personality cult towards communist party leaders. With Todor Zhivkov's coming to power in 1954, the totalitarian regime (1947-1954) gradually transformed itself into an authoritarian one, or to use the formula of the time – a 'well-developed socialist state' (Kalinova & Baeva, 2011; Znepolski, 2011). Zhivkov ruled Bulgaria for 35 years, until the fall of the communist regime in 1989. Over the years, the regime consolidated, easing the repressions amid general mass apathy and lack of resistance to this 'well-developed socialist state'. An organised dissident

movement was only born at the end of 1987-early 1988, provoked by the ecological crisis of the Chernobyl catastrophe, gas poisoning of Ruse and a campaign forcing the assimilation of ethnic Turks (Smilova, 2023). During its last waning years, the regime sought re-legitimation through ethnic nationalism – the milestone of the social contract in Bulgaria before 1945. These efforts culminated in the so-called ‘Revival Process’ (Markova, 2017), attempting to forcibly rename Bulgarian Turks, as the decisive step to finalise their gradual assimilation into the dominant Bulgarian ethnic majority. Yet, the move against the largest ethnic minority backfired, becoming the decisive catalyst of the chain of events that led to the final collapse of the communist regime in Bulgaria (Avramov, 2016).

Starting as a palace coup against Todor Zhivkov, the transition to democracy in Bulgaria was slow and hesitant (Tomini, 2014), but largely peaceful. Even though organised dissident movements in Bulgaria emerged comparatively late (Kabakchieva & Hristova, 2012), Bulgarian society was actively involved in the early transition period (1989-1991), when pro-democracy rallies and protests were taking place daily. In post-communist Bulgaria, the roundtable talks, and the adoption of the 1991 Constitution provided the societal compromise on which the transition to democracy was built (Smilova, 2020). The Round Table talks (January-May 1990) laid the foundations for dismantling the communist system (Zhelev, 2005, 315) and peacefully transitioning to democracy. The new Constitution, adopted in July 1991, formalised the consensus for democratically developing Bulgaria. Most Bulgarian citizens were involved in creating this new social contract – either directly through participating in the constant pro-democracy rallies (1989-1991) or by exercising their right to political representation. Turnout in the first free elections represents a still unmatched record for post-communist Bulgaria: 90.3%. Ethnic Turks were involved in this process through their representatives, the Movement for Rights and Freedoms; yet, Roma were *de facto* excluded as they lacked group-specific political representation. The emerging consensus for a transition to democracy included the implementation of tough reforms to turn Bulgaria into a market economy. After some backsliding from the consensus during the Videnov cabinet of 1995-1997 (whose policies led to hyperinflation), the largest protests in Bulgarian history reaffirmed the country's commitment to democratic governance and market reforms. These reforms paid off around 2005, when the country's economy finally reached and surpassed its pre-1989 levels. However, these pro-market reforms deepened social inequalities, with the country reaching high Gini index levels (scoring 40.8 in 2019, according to Trading Economics, 2019). Even though inequality has declined since then, Bulgaria remains the most unequal Member State in the EU, about 8 percentage points above the EU average – in 2023 its GINI of 37.2 compares to the EU average of 29.6 (Eurostat, 2025). Discrimination against the Roma and Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer and other sexual minorities (LGBTQI) is among

the highest in the EU. In mid-2023, for example, 48% of LGBTQI surveyed in Bulgaria experienced discrimination, which is the highest rate in the EU, whose average was 36%. (FRA, 2023).

Following the collapse of the financial system and mass protests that toppled Videnov's government in early 1997, the country turned away from its hesitant path towards democratisation and rapidly followed its new Euro-Atlantic objectives. EU and North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) accession were pursued jointly – in March 2004 the country joined NATO and in 2007 the country accessed the EU with Romania.

Political, social and economic inequalities

At the time of the country's EU accession, Bulgaria's democratic system was consolidated, yet only as an incomplete (Karasimeonov, 2019) or “defective” (Merkel, 2004) democracy. Like some other “arrested developers” in the region, it reached “a stagnant equilibrium, with democratic quality neither rising to converge with that of regional leaders, nor regressing” (Stanley, 2019). The country still is the most unequal EU Member State in terms of wealth distribution (Eurostat, 2025). Bulgaria also has had problems with the rule of law, high levels of minority discrimination (particularly of Roma and LGBTQI), as reported by the European Commission (2022), and continuing environmental concerns – such as municipal waste management or water management (European Commission, 2025).

This low-level consolidation of democracy in Bulgaria may account for the lack of dramatic democratic backsliding after EU accession (Smilova, 2025). Yet, deficiencies in key aspects of the democratic system, such as the rule of law and an inclusive democratic process, remain a constant source of popular discontent. Thus, after a relatively calm period, the country was rocked by mass protest mobilizations: ecological (2009-2012), anti-monopoly (2013), anti-government (2013 and 2020), mothers of children with disabilities (2015-2018), to name just a few. All of these demanded a more inclusive democratic process and a working rule of law (Smilov & Vajsova, 2013; Centre for Liberal Strategies, 2016; Dinev, 2021). After the last massive anti-government protests (2020), a period of acute political instability commenced. Over the last four years (2021-2024), democratic politics have been in a state of flux.

To conclude, post-EU accession Bulgaria is an interesting case for a society in which internal divisions and fragmentation of political representation have risen considerably, preventing a stable government. This situation suggests that many aspects of the social contract in the country are currently contested. At the same time, there are stabilising mechanisms which allow the country to stick to certain policies – low taxes, stable monetary policies, etc. These factors demonstrate that at least some elements of the social contract are in place, allowing

the country to move forward, despite severe political turbulence and a succession of parliamentary elections. One positive element, which deserves mentioning, is the convention of non-violent massive public protests. This is a corrective mechanism, which has been used in 2013 and 2020. Thus, the Bulgarian social contract could be described as a complex mixture of constitutional and legal rules on the one hand, and informal conventions on the other.

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Croatia

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Overview

Croatia as a political entity has a tortuous history. After the period of the medieval Croatian state, the country became part of the Hungarian kingdom in 1102. However, its political elite (nobility) continued to rely on so-called Croatian state right, as a basis for political autonomy and for an independent Croatian state in the future. After the 1526 Battle of Mohac, the Kingdom of Hungary (including the so-called 'Croatian lands') became part of the Habsburg Monarchy. In the 1860s, with the transformation of the Habsburg Monarchy into a specific empire called Austria-Hungary, the 'Croatian lands' did not form a single administrative unit (Gross & Szabo, 1992). This meant that 'the Croatian lands' did not have any kind of autonomy, mostly remaining under the administration of the Hungarian side of the empire. One must note that some parts of the 'Croatian lands', particularly Dalmatia, were among the poorest areas of Austria-Hungary.

After WWI, the 'Croatian lands' became part of the Kingdom of Serbs, Croats and Slovenes, ultimately becoming the Kingdom of Yugoslavia in 1929. Political life in that country was largely determined by tensions between Serbs and Croats, which occasionally resulted in political violence and murders.

In 1939, within the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, the 'Croatian lands' received significant administrative autonomy for the first time since the medieval Croatian state, as a territory called 'Croatian Banovina' (Jareb, 1995). Most of the territory currently belonging to Croatia was included, as well as some parts of today's Bosnia-Herzegovina and Serbia. This entity did not last long and was dissolved after the Axis occupation of Yugoslavia. In 1941, an expanded variant of the Croatian Banovina territory was established as the Independent State of Croatia (NDH) by the Ustasha movement, consisting of extreme Croatian nationalists (Catholics), assisted by the German Nazi occupation army. This movement conducted mass murders of Orthodox Serbs, particularly during the first years of the war. These killings were "not only incomprehensible from a moral point of view, but also unreasonable from the point of view of any realistic and feasible policy" (Jareb, 1995, p. 89). Jews were also treated "extremely and unreasonably" due to "pressure [...] from the Germans [...] to destroy [them] as soon as possible" (*ibid.*, p. 91-92). In addition to Croats and Serbs, Muslims (whom the Ustasha movement called 'Croats-Muslims') lived in a part of the Independent State of Croatia (today's Bosnia-Herzegovina). Relations with Muslims deteriorated during the war, since it

became evident that they increasingly considered Bosnia-Herzegovina as their autonomous territory. Because the Independent State of Croatia sided with the Axis Powers, it disappeared with the defeat of Hitler's Germany. However, Croatia was not considered a loser in WWII, since a strong anti-fascist movement operated in its territory. This movement was under the leadership of the Communist Party, aiming at the reconstruction of Yugoslavia based on federalist and radical-socialist ideas.

This movement also sought to re-establish trust between Croats and Serbs, which had been significantly damaged by numerous war crimes. As a sign of its success in building trust, Croatia was defined as 'the state of Croats and Serbs in Croatia' within communist Yugoslavia. The ruling Communist Party thus created a kind of social contract based on national tolerance/balance in Croatia/Yugoslavia. That social contract also had its socio-economic dimension, with an 'agreement' between the working class and the communist elite to ensure almost full employment and a relatively decent life standard (Zaslavsky, 1985; Županov, 1983). In the late 1960s and early 1970s, this 'contract' was jeopardised by a strong political movement that mainly pursued greater financial and cultural autonomy for Croatia. This movement deeply disturbed ethnic Serbs, as well as the federal authorities, who replaced the communist leadership of Croatia at the end of 1971. With that authoritarian 'coup', the struggle for independence was temporarily postponed. Although national independence was put aside, the 'socialist' part of the Croatian social contract remained alive. Namely, Croats could continue to make their living from renting accommodation, a tendency that dates to late socialism. In the early 1980s, many Croats took out loans to build their summer homes. Inflation in the 1990s significantly devalued them and practically erased large amounts of that debt, laying the foundations for the petite bourgeoisie to turn Croatia into a tourist paradise.

Opposition parties were created at the end of the 1980s, which led to the first multi-party elections in 1990, and to the Croatian Democratic Union (HDZ) replacing the Communist Party in the government (Grdešić et al., 1991). It seemed that the initial transition to democracy was of the consensual type. However, Croatia was soon attacked by the Yugoslav federal army and rebel Serbs who tried to separate parts of the Croatian territory where they lived as an ethnic majority. The war for independence successfully ended in 1995. The war also had another face, where Croatia militarily helped the Croats living in Bosnia-Herzegovina. This policy was never well received by Bosnians (former Muslims) and their relations with Croats remained relatively tense. On the one hand, Bosnians believed Croats (and the Republic of Croatia) were trying to separate territories where they were still the ethnic majority. On the other hand, Croats constantly complained of being subjected to majoritarianism by Bosnians in Bosnia-Herzegovina.

Regarding the transition to democracy, we can conceptually introduce two phases of the transition in Croatia (Čular, 2005, p. 1; Kursar & Matan, 2020, p. 131). Its first phase began in the late 1980s and the second with the 2000 elections, which meant "the beginning of the consolidation of democracy in Croatia" (Čular, 2005, p. 1). Čular considers that a key factor, among the "standard indicators of consolidation", was "elections that result[ed] in a peaceful change of parties in power" (*ibid.*). Namely, HDZ stepped down from power in favour of a six-party coalition led by the Social Democratic Party (SDP).

Since the 2004 elections, HDZ regained power and has mostly remained there ever since (except for 2011-2015, when another SDP-led coalition held power). Apart from the 1990s, HDZ has been more interested in a moderate conservative style of ruling, rather than an antiliberal or authoritarian one. Its prolonged ruling, however, has created the conditions for widespread corruption. This corruption greatly threatens the social contract of Croatia as a small, but orderly and relatively prosperous state that, as a member of the EU and NATO, truly promotes 'European values'.

Croatia has been experiencing a sudden economic boom in recent years. In 2024, the GDP growth rate was close to 4%. The sources of this growth are "huge subsidies from European funds" that will "reach 3.9 percent of GDP (Gross Domestic Product)" (Vizek, 2024). Hence, Croatia has "growth in government spending and company investments [...]" but also growth in household spending" (*ibid.*). However, this growth probably will not last forever, as labour productivity and industrial production are steadily declining, while EU funds are drying up (*ibid.*).

Since Croatia is extremely dependent on tourism (25% of its national income), more real estate is being converted to rental accommodations. Therefore, the government struggles to introduce any kind of real estate tax. It seems that "the extremely low amount of real estate tax introduced for the first time (...) will not motivate citizens to stop treating apartments as a savings and investment product" (Visek, 2025). It goes without saying that this tax "should be significantly higher (...) to (...) thwart the demand for apartments that are not used for housing" (*ibid.*). Thereby, Croatia will possibly avoid permanent "increases in residential real estate prices and the reduction of housing affordability" (*ibid.*). In this regard, the opposition parties do not offer a new social contract, but rather a 'genuine' (anti-corruption) realisation of the old one. Therefore, Croatia is faced with a gradual, consensual transformation of its social contract, with only external circumstances appearing to force any real change. These forces could come from the EU, which is exposed to growing pressures, ranging from technological, economic, geopolitical and even ideological. This push could be beneficial for Croatia, whose ongoing social consensus seems to be counting its final days.

Political, social and economic inequalities

Regarding national minorities, Serbs are the largest ethnic minority (today 3.2% of the population compared to 12.2% in 1991). Since the end of the war for independence (1995), serious efforts have been made to improve the political and legal status of all ethnic minorities. In fact, they are today part of the social contract that HDZ promotes by making efforts to place them with other minorities in the government. This primarily concerns the Serbian national minority, which has mainly left Croatia during the 1990s. The first elements of a social contract between the majority Croatian community and minority Serbs were established in the country's constitutional law, guaranteeing the presence of Serbs in various local and state authorities. Noticeable improvements were only made in 2003, when Prime Minister Ivo Sanader (HDZ) came to power. He invited Serbian political representatives to join the government, which initiated a break with the prior politics of turbulent ethnic conflict in Croatia. All subsequent governments were also supportive towards the Serbian community, although some of its rights were often denied at the local level. In Eastern Slavonia, ethnic Croatian populations in the city of Vukovar contested the right to Cyrillic inscriptions and Serbian language on administrative buildings. Local Croats fought against it, even though the Serbian community had a legal right to such inscriptions, since Serbs constituted more than (the legally required) one-third of the city's population. As the number of Serbs in Vukovar later declined, and their numbers fell below one-third, they lost their right to linguistic representation.

Sexual minorities are not particularly supported by the wider population. However, within the political elite, there is a near consensus that these minorities are an indispensable part of the social contract and all its future transformations (Kursar & Matan, 2022).

Regarding the rights of women, "the Croatian parliament may be categorized somewhere between the Central European and the Scandinavian parliaments when it comes to the share of women, with the Socialist party family being a real trend-setter" (Ilišin & Čular, 2014, p. 178). Today, women represent 25% of the parliament but still earn relatively less than men in the private sector.

It seems that environmental issues are not a priority in Croatian politics. Croatia has a problem with where to store the nuclear waste from the Krško nuclear power plant. The same applies to regular municipal waste, as local populations often resist garbage disposal in their communities. Occasionally, there are relatively successful protests against the construction of mini-hydroelectric power plants in mountainous regions. Croatia's socio-economic development is quite unequal, since the population prefers to live in the four larger cities and on the coast, mostly due to tourism. This distribution contributes to the tremendous depopulation and impoverishment of rural areas, whose inhabitants often leave Croatia. For

example, the agricultural region of Slavonia has the highest level of social exclusion in Croatia (Matković & Štulhofer, 2006, 9).

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Finland

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Overview

The history of Finland is deeply entwined with the imperial struggles of its two powerful neighbours: Sweden and Russia. Under Swedish rule, Finland was considered to cover regions in the East rather than a polity of any kind. A more explicit formation of 'Finland' as a distinct political entity only developed after the Russian Empire granted autonomy to Finland in 1809. The shifting power structures influenced the formation of a political culture and practices which have navigated shifting allegiances, developed strategic resistance and advanced political pragmatism. This historical balancing act has shaped Finland's national identity, which is manifested by some commonly recognised elements in reproduced narratives. For example, the widely cherished concept of '*sisu*' (which roughly translates to 'grit') is a mixture of resilience, perseverance and clever manoeuvring. The experience of living under both Swedish and Russian rule has informed Finland's long-standing official foreign policy of neutrality. This narrative and practice have gradually become contested and complex since the dissolving of the Soviet Union (for an overview of the shift and emerging debates, see Aunesluoma & Rainio-Niemi, 2016; Tiilikainen, 2015).

The legacies of Swedish and Russian rule are evident in Finland's legislative and institutional frameworks, as well as its linguistic and cultural landscapes. Western and Eastern Finland bear the imprints of these imperial pasts, with Swedish influence predominantly notable in the West and the South, while Russian legacies are more pronounced in the East. The borderlands, particularly in Karelia, serve as living testaments to the flux of history. The trauma of losing Karelia to Russia after WWII, and the subsequent resettlement of refugees, deeply impacted national policies and social cohesion in Finland (Fingerroos, 2012). These occurrences influenced discussions about demographic changes, and minorities and majorities in Finland overtime (*ibid.*).

Beyond the East-West divide, the North-South question and the marginalisation of Eastern Finland further complicate Finland's regional dynamics. Anti-elitism and the rural-urban divide have long been a part of the country's political discourse (Alapuro, 1976; Karvonen, 2000, Kuhmonen & Kuhmonen, 2015; Kumpulainen & Soini, 2019). The post-war era, particularly under President Urho Kekkonen (presidency from 1956-1982), saw policies aimed at keeping the entire country inhabited, reinforcing Finland's social contract and mitigating regional

disparities. This approach has endured, although the contemporary realities of economic centralisation challenge its sustainability.

While Finland often positions itself outside the European colonial narrative, its historical and ongoing relationship with the Sámi people tells a different story (Nyyssönen, 2013). The Sámi, an Indigenous people whose homeland, Sápmi, extends across Norway, Sweden, Finland and Russia, have faced systematic marginalisation by all nation-states involved (McGuire, 2022; Valkonen & Valkonen, 2018). The Finnish state has long engaged in practices that resemble colonialism – limiting Sámi land rights, imposing Finnish-language education and failing to fully recognise Sámi self-governance. This history continues to shape contemporary debates over land use, environmental policies and minority rights (Valkonen, 2018). While recent years have seen increased activism and awareness of Sámi issues, true autonomy remains unresolved. Finland's reluctance to ratify the International Labour Organization's (ILO) Convention 169 on Indigenous and Tribal Peoples underscores the tensions between national governance and international human rights frameworks.

Unlike many European states, Finland has not possessed overseas colonies, creating a national self-image distinct from traditional colonial powers. However, recent scholarly discussions have begun to explore Finland's involvement in colonial enterprises, particularly in Africa, though this remains a largely underexamined aspect of the nation's past (Särkkä, 2015). The colonialist aspects have also been reflected in the literature on racism in Finland, its particularities and connections to international debates, discussing how the Finnish sense of exceptionalism as a country outside of colonialism, as a country with a history of being oppressed, continue to uphold racism (for an overview, see Hoegaerts et al., 2022; especially the Introduction in the same volume).

In sum, Finland's historical trajectory has fostered a self-understanding, which has been shaped by a dual legacy of imperial subjugation and strategic independence. Part of this discourse, embedded over decades in history education and foreign policy narratives, has emphasised resilience and diplomatic agility. However, recent extensive research on the injustices against the Sámi, as well as critical literature on the civil war (1918; see e.g. Tepora & Roselius 2014), the winter war (1939-1940; see Kleemola, 2022 especially for the symbolic meaning of nation building) and the continuation war (1941-1944), have pushed forward new internal reflections. These reflections focus on the treatment of minorities and dissidents, in the name of national security and state independence.

The development of democratic culture and institutions in Finland has also included undercurrents, and even explicit aspirations, towards authoritarianism. In the late 19th century, Finland was navigating the balance between constructing political and democratic institutions,

while simultaneously operating under Russian rule (for an overview of the formation of political language and institutions, see Hyvärinen et al., 2003). This tension culminated in the sweeping parliamentary reform of 1906, a defining moment that introduced universal suffrage and reshaped the nation's political framework (on the formation of the Finnish Eduskunta into a parliament, see Pekonen, 2021). Despite the turmoil of the 1918–1919 Civil War, Finland managed to uphold its parliamentary democracy and develop its representative structures, open to women's participation (Sulkunen 2019).

In the 1930s, the rise of the far-right Lapua Movement, an explicitly anti-democratic force, sought to suppress leftist elements and impose an authoritarian order. Though ultimately dismantled, the legacy of the Lapua Movement lingered in Finnish political memory. Decades later, echoes of this illiberal tradition have resurfaced in contemporary far-right rhetoric, as scholars like Salojärvi et al. (2023) have noted. The literature on the history of authoritarian far-right movements and politics in Finland has recently been increasing. Studies are now also seeking to understand the links between the historical legacy and contemporary movements (e.g., Kotonen & Sallamaa 2023; Kotonen 2014). Despite the presidency of Tarja Halonen, and the three female prime ministers (Anneli Jäätteenmäki, Mari Kiviniemi and Sanna Marin), the tradition of strong, often male-dominated presidential leadership has persisted well into the 2020s, as an integral part of the country's democratic structures (for a recent gender equality assessment from the Finnish Parliament, see Erikson et al., 2024). Finland's parliamentary model, which combines strong parliamentary power with presidential power weaved into shared leadership between the government and the president in foreign policy, continues to underline the role of a strong individual leadership.

Over the decades, Finland maintained close, if at times uneasy, ties between the Soviet Union and Western Europe, with political structures that helped to internally support and grow strong civil society organisations and activity. The Lutheran Church in Finland has also played a crucial part in the formation of the social contract, acting as a key institution between the state and civil society, during both peace and wartime (Markkola, 2011; Tilli, 2016). As part of the political and public discourses, Finland has continued to position itself as a country resisting Russian imperialism – a stance that has only intensified considering geopolitical tensions since 2022. The practical openness of the Finland-Russia border throughout history for everyday exchanges (except during the Soviet rule and post-2022 period) highlights the complexities of Finnish-Russian relations.

The development of a strong military culture in Finland has also been linked to the building of state independence and political institutions (for an analysis from a historical and conceptual perspective, see Kettunen 2018). Built on the narrative of self-defence against the Soviet Union and Russia especially, the upkeep of a strong military over decades has kept translating

into a resolute willingness to defend the country (Häkkinen & Kaarkoski, 2022). This tradition and mindset were also visible in political and public discourses, when applying for NATO membership in 2022, in the strong support for membership expressed in polls and debates.

Political, social and economic inequalities

For much of its history, Finland was among the poorest nations in Europe, with an economy rooted in agrarian traditions and local cultures (Peltonen, 1988; Jäntti, 2006). Yet, through deliberate social policies and a strong emphasis on civic education, the country steadily lifted itself out of poverty and was among one of the wealthiest countries in the world by the 1980s (Kettunen, 2001). The expansion of free education and development of a robust welfare state, not only transformed Finland's economic landscape, but also played a subtle role in deradicalisation, fostering a sense of national cohesion (Kuokkanen et al., 2023).

At the heart of Finland's social contract lies a strong, historically and politically constructed idea of the welfare state, built on the cornerstones of basic education, social and healthcare systems, as well as a modest gap between income levels (see Kettunen, 2001; Hakoniemi, 2021; 2025). Even with a strong right-wing, conservative political climate, the protection of the welfare state and services has largely been an acceptable part of the political narrative. However, there are signs that the ideological polarisation of recent years has resulted in more contested views on the organisation and level of basic services, as well as a broader acceptance of greater income inequality (for a quantitative analysis, see Im et al, 2021).

For decades, Finland's labour market has been defined by tripartite industrial agreements, where trade unions, industrial elites and the government work in collaboration. These negotiations have reinforced a system where political and economic power has been deeply intertwined (Alaja, 2011). However, this structure has begun to crumble, reflecting wider global trends of deregulation and shifting labour dynamics (Jonker-Hoffrén, 2019). More research is needed to see how this shift starts to affect the party politics and political climate in Finland.

Gender equality has a relatively long institutional history in Finland, where granting women political rights and agency took place relatively early (for a recent Nordic overview, see Eriksson & Freidenvall, 2024). Legislative equity developed towards a broader European approach when Finland joined the European Union in 1995 (Kantola et al., 2012), with an inclusive Marriage Act (2017) and the recent Act on Legal Recognition of Gender (2023).

Perhaps one of the most enduring elements of the Finnish identity is its deep connection to nature (Periäinen, 2006; Hakoköngäs & Puhakka, 2023). This connection has both cultural and economic dimensions through traditional industry (such as forestry), as well as in the constituting of some forms of political activism and agency (Hiedanpää, 2002; Berglund, 2001;

Raatikainen et al., 2024). Traditional industries (such as forestry, peat extraction and mining) have been dominating the economic landscape. Now, these industries are at the heart of reshaping the ecosocial contract in Finland, through the contested milieu of sustainability transformation and the political battles over environmental policy. The fur industry, a long-standing point of contention, is an example of the tensions between economic activity and traditional livelihoods, regional and local politics and claims for animal wellbeing and rights. The ecosocial contract in Finland therefore means a politically, economically, locally and culturally complex context for renegotiating the historical urban-rural divide, the structure and nature of economic and political elites, national identity and the possibility of an ecosocially just welfare state model.

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France

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Overview

The French social contract, rooted in the revolutionary ideals of liberty, equality and fraternity, has deep historical foundations shaped by colonialism/imperialism and authoritarianism. These twin forces have moulded France's political and social structures, continuing to influence its modern identity and governance. In this contribution, we highlight crucial aspects of the long-term social contract, which shaped past social arrangements. As Mills (1997) argued, existing social contracts must be studied historically, revealing exclusionary features and the concentration of power in the hands of the few. Understanding this legacy is particularly relevant today, as France grapples with internal tensions – over immigration, territorial inequality and national memory – and its role on the global stage within the EU and United Nations (UN).

Studying the long-term social contract is essential to comprehend: (i) current contestations of central authority and territorial disparity, which echo historical patterns of exclusion and control; and (ii) the specific challenges France faces, such as reconciling its universalist ideals with a colonial/imperial and authoritarian past. This study explores how colonialism, imperialism and authoritarianism have intertwined to form the social contract's bedrock, how they perpetuate inequalities and exclusion, and how these roots are contested in contemporary debates. We will examine each force separately before connecting them to current challenges, concluding with their implications for France's social fabric.

Colonialism: The Empire's Lasting Influence

France's colonial history has left an enduring imprint on its social contract. Stretching across continents (from Africa to Asia and the Americas), this empire's remnants linger in territories like Mayotte and Nouvelle-Calédonie, starkly evidencing a past steeped in domination and paternalistic control (Cogneau et al., 2024). Colonialism entrenched rigid hierarchies, epitomised by Jules Ferry's late 19th century claim that France had a duty to 'civilise' lesser races, a doctrine that sat uneasily with the egalitarian promises of the 1789 Revolution (Girardet, 1972). Though France abolished slavery in 1794 and again in 1848, Napoleon's reversal in 1802 underscored a recurring conflict between lofty ideals and exploitative realities.

This colonial inheritance ignites persistent struggles over identity, equity and belonging, which fracture contemporary French society. The Algerian War's (1954-1962) brutal legacy and fraught process of decolonisation remain etched in collective memory. This tension was

acknowledged by President Emmanuel Macron in 2017 when he labelled colonisation a “crime against humanity,” while noting its complex outcomes. Overall, France’s relationship with its former African colonies remains complex and marked by neocolonialism (Vermeren, 2023). These struggles are far from static; they shift with political currents, demographic transformations and global influences, keeping the colonial past a volatile force in France’s present. Today, descendants of colonised peoples face inequalities – evident in social exclusion and economic disadvantage – challenging the social contract’s pledge of equality (Casali, 2015). This history also underpins territorial divides, with overseas regions lagging the *Métropole* in development, a disparity that reflects colonial neglect.

Moreover, the colonial legacy shapes current debates on Islamophobia and immigration, amplifying tensions over national identity. It also shapes social and economic disparities of overseas territories (Huillery, 2009; Infante-Amate & Krausmann, 2019) and is instrumentalized by far-right stakeholders to introduce exclusionary elements into the French social contract (Mondon, 2022). Many immigrants hail from former colonies, particularly in North and West Africa. Their presence fuels controversies over integration and cultural difference, debates often tinged with Islamophobic rhetoric. Policies perceived as discriminatory, alongside societal attitudes rooted in colonial hierarchies, exacerbate feelings of alienation, ultimately making the French social contract’s promise of fraternity elusive. These dynamics highlight how colonialism remains a live wire, driving ongoing contention in France’s diverse, post-colonial society.

Authoritarianism has profoundly shaped France’s social contract, forging a lasting tradition of centralised power that stretches from the absolutist reign of Louis XIV (1643-1715) to the contemporary era. Under Louis XIV, the monarchy consolidated authority by diminishing regional influence, laying the groundwork for a state-centric model that prioritised control over the fostering and incorporation of diversity (Morill, 1978). This pattern solidified under Napoleon Bonaparte (1769-1821), whose militarised regime transformed revolutionary fervour into a disciplined consolidation of power. The French Revolution’s own authoritarian turn, during the Reign of Terror (1793-1794), followed by Napoleon III’s restrictive Second Empire (1852-1870), further entrenched this tendency (Gainot, 2015). The Vichy regime’s collaboration with Nazi Germany in 1940 stands as a grim pinnacle of this legacy, suspending liberties and enforcing repression (Jenkins, 2005). Across these periods, authoritarianism entrenched a reliance on strong, top-down governance, a hallmark that persists in France’s political DNA (Lascoumbes & Le Galès, 2004; Prasad, 2005; Cole, 2008).

This tradition extended into the colonial era, when France ruled its overseas territories with unyielding control, often disregarding local consent. The suppression of dissent, exemplified by the 1945 Sétif massacre in Algeria, mirrored domestic crackdowns and reinforced a

governance style that favoured order over negotiation (Montagnon, 2010). Today, this legacy endures in the Fifth Republic, established by Charles de Gaulle in 1958, which vests the presidency with extensive powers. This robust, centralised structure often prioritises state sovereignty over individual or communal autonomy. Policies like the 2004 headscarf ban, enforcing secularism, or the 2015 state of emergency – extended multiple times and rooted in colonial precedents from the Algerian War – reflect an authoritarian streak that can alienate citizens, particularly marginalised groups that feel targeted (Weill, 2014; Reynolds, 2017; Zinigrad, 2025). Such measures, while framed as protective, underscore a tension between state authority and personal freedom.

Overall, historical authoritarianism has birthed a dual legacy within the social contract: a deep-seated expectation that the state will act as a guarantor of welfare, education and security, coupled with a counter-current of scepticism and resistance. The French Revolution itself emerged as a rejection of absolutist rule, embedding a culture of protest into the national fabric, evident in movements like the May 1968 uprisings and the more recent *gilets jaunes* (Yellow Vests). The colonial experience amplified this dynamic: authoritarian governance abroad, such as the brutal suppression of Algerian resistance, paralleled domestic clampdowns, like Vichy's repressive apparatus. This duality persists today, breeding a complex relationship with the state. Citizens demand that the state upholds *égalité* and *fraternité*, yet harbour distrust when its heavy hand echoes past repressions. This contention is seen, for instance, in ongoing debates over police brutality in the banlieues, where communities feel the weight of historical control rather than inclusion (Balibar, 2007; Schneider, 2018; Silverstein, 2018).

Exclusion has been a cornerstone of France's authoritarian regimes, whether through the class hierarchies of the monarchy or Vichy's racial collaboration with Nazi ideology. Colonial authoritarianism intensified this issue, imposing stark divides between the colonisers and the colonised, with racial and cultural superiority as its bedrock. This legacy undermines the social contract's promise of universal equality by perpetuating systemic biases. The French state's colourblind approach – refusing to collect ethnic statistics – aims at universality, while also reflecting the country's (post) colonial aphasia regarding its colonial past (Amiriaux and Simon, 2006). Yet this approach often obscures inequalities tied to colonial and authoritarian pasts, such as the disproportionately high incarceration rates among North African descendants. This historical comfort with exclusionary governance challenges the inclusivity at the heart of *fraternité*, leaving marginalised groups on the periphery of the social contract.

Authoritarian periods have also normalised a pronounced focus on security, a trait amplified by the colonial rule's need to subdue restive populations. Napoleon's militarised state and Vichy's police apparatus set precedents for a strong security orientation, while events like the

Sétif massacre highlighted the colonial reliance on force (Montagnon, 2010). Today, this manifests in a social contract that balances liberty with an emphasis on order, evident in France's robust anti-terrorism laws and handling of protests. The 2015 state of emergency and its derogation from France's constitutional and international law obligations to protect civil and political rights, draw directly from colonial-era legal tools, such as martial law, curfews, administrative detentions and elimination of institutions, circumvention of judicial institutions, exclusion of indigenous populations of benefits and rights enjoyed by the colonizer, and more generally, the excessive use of executive decrees followed by the normalization of emergency powers through codification. This has been raising alarms about civil liberties, particularly among communities historically subjected to authoritarian oversight (Reynolds, 2017). While citizens accept heightened security as part of the state's protective role, this strains *liberté* when perceived as overreaching, especially in areas where the echoes of colonial control still resonate.

Political, social and economic inequalities

The enduring influence of colonialism and authoritarianism informs France's contemporary social contract. The Fifth Republic, with its centralised presidency, carries forward an authoritarian heritage. Erupting in 2018, the Yellow Vests protests laid bare this friction, decrying territorial inequality as thriving urban centres outpace neglected rural and peri-urban zones. Similarly, overseas territories like Nouvelle-Calédonie expose lingering colonial wounds, where unrest signals a failure to deliver on the promise of equality, echoing disparities forged in the imperial past.

Immigration, intertwined with colonial history, stirs fierce contention over identity and belonging. Many immigrants from former colonies, particularly North and West Africa, face exclusionary pressures amplified by far-right rhetoric. Economic and social hierarchies persist, creating a gap between principle and practice, as the social contract struggles to reconcile its universalist ambitions with lived realities and unequal starting points (Chabal, 2015; Barwick & Beaman, 2019).

Debates over memory exemplify the country's enduring legacy of colonialism and authoritarianism. The Vichy regime's collaboration with Nazi Germany and Napoleon's reimposition of slavery in 1802 linger as unhealed scars in public discourse, much like the colonial rule. The 2001 Taubira Law, recognising slavery as a crime against humanity, is important. Yet, the history of colonialism and its consequences for France's territories remains a vivid object of discussion (Barkley, 2013), as exemplified by the recent suspension of journalist Jean-Michel Apathie, after his critique of French colonialism in Algeria. These

tensions have crystallised in recent years through high-profile identity discussions. In the 2010s, Nicolas Sarkozy's push for a national debate on French identity stirred controversy, followed by François Bayrou's 2025 proposition to revisit "what it is to be French." Such initiatives reflect unease with a past that resists closure, challenging the social contract to bridge historical divides with a shared sense of belonging.

On the global stage, France's roles in the EU and the UN project influence, yet interventions like those in Mali hint at colonial echoes, prompting scrutiny of its international responsibility. Domestically, this outward reach deepens scepticism when economic globalisation widens gaps, as underscored by the Yellow Vests' critique of an elitist state. Environmental pressures add another layer: top-down climate policies, often clashing with local needs, reinforcing perceptions of an authoritarian disconnect. Together, these contestations – spanning territory, identity, equity, memory and governance – test the French social contract's capacity to evolve.

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Germany

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Overview

The reception of the German past is mainly shaped by the legacy of National Socialism, the Holocaust and later state socialism in Eastern Germany (1945-1990). To this day, questions of guilt and responsibility after Auschwitz, as historical singularity, frame the current social contract and continue to constitute contentious debates. After the reunification, unequal experiences with 'double dictatorship' (Kühnhardt, 1996) exposed several new dividing lines and ruptures that relate to these past experiences and their politics of memory. In the following, we describe the deep roots of the social contract and their *longue durée* into contemporary controversies and frictions in the German social contract. We portray the deep roots in broader terms, since Germany's historical nation-building process has greatly impacted Europe and other European societies.

Germany's contemporary borders have only been in place since reunification in the 1990s. Initially, Germany's nation-building process was slow compared with other European countries (Epkenhans, 2011). Up until 1871, various principalities and other administrative entities formed changing alliances, associations and unions of what would later become the geopolitical shapes of first imperial Germany, then Nazi Germany and only recently of the Federal Republic of Germany and, until 1990, the German Democratic Republic. Located at the centre of the continent, the borders of Germany – to be understood as a deliberately generic term here – were repeatedly subject to change. Wars triggered by neighbours, but above all conflicts caused by German rulers themselves, were responsible for the various shapes the so-called Holy Roman Empire of the German Nation took over the course of 360 years (Epkenhans, 2011). Externally the dimension of the then German Empire bordered Denmark in the north, Switzerland to the south, and in the southeast, it extended to the Adriatic Sea with the Duchy of Carniola and to the border of Hungary with Austria, Bohemia and Moravia. In the west, it extended to the Netherlands and France, including the Spanish Netherlands – today's Belgium and parts of northern France – as well as the Free County of Burgundy. To the east, it bordered Poland, but included Hinterpommern and Silesia (*ibid.*, 159-160). The Empire began to fray at the fringes already in the second half of the 17th century, particularly on its western border. In the west, territories were lost to France in its successful attempts to secure the natural Rhine border by classic wars of conquest as well as territorial exchange. Among 'the darkest chapters' in European and German history of the 18th century are the three partitions of Poland where the greed of the Western powers of Prussia, Austria

and Russia created new borders (*ibid.*, 161-162). With the end of the Thirty Years' War in 1648, the German Empire internally comprised approximately 300 independent secular and ecclesiastical territories, plus 1,400 imperial knightships and 51 free imperial cities. A unificatory process was brought about by the Napoleonic Wars between 1792 and 1815 during which the number of territories and states was reduced to 37 (*ibid.*, 162-3).

In 1871, the German Empire (in German historiography, this period is called *Deutsches Kaiserreich*) under Emperor Wilhelm I, emerged as an authoritarian state with a powerful agrarian-aristocratic elite. Then, Otto von Bismarck became imperial chancellor (1871-1890). Bismarck's diplomatic focus was on the maintenance of European peace – which, however, included a strong military component of coercion and intervention. After his forced resignation in 1890 and the enthronement of Emperor Wilhelm II (1888), Imperial Germany's outlook on foreign policy changed from seeking to maintain peace to building alliances capable of withstanding war (Stürmer, 1985; Ullmann, 1995).

At the invitation of Chancellor Otto von Bismarck, representatives from 14 imperial powers gathered in 1884-85 for the so-called Berlin 'Africa Conference' to agree on rules for further colonising Africa and staking out their claims to ownership in Africa. Not a single representative from Africa itself was present. Initially hesitant about Germany's alleged need for overseas colonies, rapid economic growth and industrialisation led Bismarck and his successors to pursue imperial expansion overseas much more forcefully. Imperial Germany's colonial rule, while short (1884-1918), culminated in the first genocide of the 20th century on the resisting Nama and Herero peoples in southwestern Africa (today's Namibia). In 1904 and 1905 respectively, Lieutenant General Lothar von Trotha, head of the colonial troops, ordered the complete annihilation of the Herero and Nama. It is estimated that 100,000 people were killed (Brehl, 2004; Häussler, 2018).

In contrast to other former European colonial powers, there is little immigration from the former colonies. So, this period of formal colonialism cannot be said to constitute a central pillar in the deep roots of Germany's contemporary social contract and its frictions. In the metropole, accelerated industrialisation met with the heightened nationalism of Imperial Germany. The notion of the nation was originally directed against aristocratic rule, emphasising ideas around popular sovereignty. With the foundation of Imperial Germany, nationalism played a crucial role in overcoming traditional regional forms of identification. A very readily available means for Nation-building through nationalism benefited significantly from the construction of enemy images. Conjuring enemy images became the prime means for constructing a German national identity, previously underdeveloped (Walkenhorst, 1995).

At the same time, tension rose with rival England. After a stretch of diplomatic shifts and changes in the early 20th century, imperial Germany feared it would be encircled by this enemy. Heightened 'negative' nationalism internally, combined with a sense of threat and isolation externally, ignited Germany's declarations of war and the ensuing WWI that lasted from 1914 to 1918 (Hildebrandt, 1995).

Imperial Germany's defeat in WWI marked the end of the *Kaiserreich* and its overseas colonies. In 1919, the so-called Weimar Republic was proclaimed. Central constitutional principles were popular sovereignty, the separation of powers and basic rights. Structurally, the Weimar Republic was a parliamentary democracy. Women were granted the right to vote in 1918.

The Weimar Republic was characterised by intense political and economic struggles, upheavals and revolts. From today's vantage point, the Weimar Republic is perceived as very unstable, a fragile social and political construct, plagued by major shortcomings in terms of its institutional set-up (Fink, 1996; Berman, 1997; Hett, 2018; Lehmann, 2019). This is because, the ultimate crisis of the Weimar Republic is held to be the accession to power by Adolf Hitler and his nationalist-fascist party, the *Nationalsozialistische Deutsche Arbeiterpartei* (NSDAP), through constitutional means.

While it is debatable whether contemporaries of the Weimar Republic experienced this time as a period of instability, the idea of 'Weimar = crisis' reverberates strongly in the contemporary German imaginary. One central pillar of West Germany's social contract, post-WWII, is a distancing from this crises-ridden period. 'Bonn [West Germany's capital] is not Weimar' became the credo of the newly founded Federal Republic. Furthermore, Weimar became a metaphor for all things that needed to be prevented through a more robust democratic framework (Leonhard, 2018; Wirsching, 2007).

The possibility that democracy can democratically abolish itself, and that unimaginable horrors will ensue, has become a major narrative reaching far beyond the contemporary German democratic imaginary (Moyn, 2010; Heerten, 2011; 2014; Eckel, 2014). Indeed, this mythologised notion of Weimar seems to also feed into today's agitated discourse on the erosion of liberal democracy in Western societies (for an informative analysis, see Przeworski 2019).

Hitler made no secret about his antidemocratic ambitions. Immediately after coming to power in 1933, *Gleichschaltung* [enforced conformity] of state and society began. Under Nazi rule, with mass popular support, Germany was turned into a totalitarian state seeking to create a 'new human' by breaking up traditional social and political structures. Mass organisations,

surveillance and terror were meant to generate a new society and a new individual (Arendt, 2017 [1966]).

The totalitarian Nazi regime established a dictatorship based on an ideology of nation, race and leader. The aim of National Socialist policy was to create a 'people's community' [*Volksgemeinschaft*], a social order to which only the 'hereditarily valuable' and 'racially pure' Germans belonged. Thus, the 'foreign races' [*Fremdrassige*] and 'strangers to the people' [*Fremdvölkische*], above all Jewish people, were to be excluded. Inclusion and exclusion are therefore the two inseparable sides of the National Socialist national community (Jochheim, 2016; see also Schmitz-Berning, 2007).

Promoting an ideology of inclusion versus exclusion in the harshest terms imaginable – that of worthy versus unworthy life – also rationalised a politics of so-called 'living space-extension'. 'Lebensraum im Osten' ('living space in the East') was a propaganda term referring to the idea that racially pure Germans needed more living space, which was to be acquired by colonising Eastern Europe. Eastern Europe was available, according to Nazi ideology, as it was populated by inferior Slavic peoples (Kletzin, 2002). While not the sole driving force, Hitler's invasion of Poland in 1939 (initiating WWII) closely relates to the Nazi idea and implementation of 'living space' [*Lebensraum*] and 'living space politics' [*Lebensraumpolitik*] (see for instance, Kienemann, 2018).

From the very beginning, fanatic antisemitism constituted the core of Hitler and then Nazi ideology – an ideology that found easy uptake in the German population. With the rise of the NSDAP, Jewish people were subjected to more frequent and increasingly open terrorisation. Violence against Jews was by no means restricted to state authorities; instead, acts of treason, abandonment and violence were likewise committed by 'normal' people. At the conference of Wannsee in 1941, a close circle of Hitler's intimates planned the 'final solution to the Jewish question'. This planned genocide of Jews, in a meticulous technical-logistical manner, would later become known as the Holocaust or Shoa. Millions of European Jews were deported and killed by the Nazi regime, as were hundreds of thousands of other people who had fallen prey to the ideology of 'unworthy life' [*lebensunwertes Leben*]. Outside of the extermination camps, millions of non-Jewish Eastern European civilians were killed.

In May 1945, Germany was defeated by the Allied Forces. The country largely laid in ruins and was occupied by United States (US), Russian, British and French Forces. After initially establishing four occupational zones in 1949, two German States were founded: the Western Federal Republic of Germany (under US, French and British Forces) and the Eastern German Democratic Republic (under the Russian Army). Western Germany shortly became part of NATO and the EU, while Eastern Germany joined the Warsaw Pact. Without full sovereignty

and under occupation, Germany was a divided country and a battlefield for the Cold War. Germany was only to obtain full sovereignty after reunification in 1990.

Political, social and economic inequalities

How, if at all, does one 'come back' from this violent history as a nation? What is the meaning of guilt and responsibility? What, considering this history, does it mean to be German and what is Germany in the world? There are no easy or straightforward answers. Yet this seeking of, or desire to seek, answers to seemingly unanswerable questions (see Adorno, 2020 [1966]), remains pressing. Such highly contentious questions coin Germany's social contract in both legal and socio-political terms, as well as its fractions, even today.

Some problems associated with being the heir of *Kaiserreich*, 'Weimar' and 'Auschwitz' have been solved legally: Holocaust denial is a crime in Germany, as is displaying Nazi insignia or using certain figures of speech; hate speech in general constitutes a criminal offense. Germany's post-WWII constitution, the Basic Law, was drafted to break with the past. It thus emphasises the inviolability of human dignity and human rights, alongside the idea of militant democracy (*wehrhafte Demokratie*; Thiel, 2003), with a strong separation of powers and a commitment to European integration. Wars of aggression are forbidden by the Basic Law. Today, Germany still has a 'parliamentary army', an army that is controlled by the parliament rather than the head of government or the minister of defense.

Beyond the legally regulated realm, however, controversies continue to arise. One of the most controversial issues is the question of the Holocaust's singularity: what it means to constitute a barbaric singularity in civilisational history; how something that is understood as incomparable still holds the danger of repetition; how to prevent 'this' from happening ever again, with a shifting and sometimes peculiarly shapeless 'this'.

Some unresolved issues regarding historical guilt, responsibility and the 'never again' were subdued by Western Germany's economic success in the post-WWII period, bringing a kind of materialistic consumerism (Hertfeld, 2017). Externally, this success raised old fears, thus, Germany's deep integration into the European Union became the precondition for accepting its hegemonic position and restoring its sovereignty.

Internally, the economic sedative has been wearing off from the late 1960s onwards. Contemporary debates revolve around the culture and politics of memory but also state societal and individual responsibility, turning this debate into questions concerning freedom of expression (see Friese, 2024; Assmann, 2024). Historical guilt and responsibility as part of the German national identity, as well as the proclaimed German state's *raison d'être*, pose questions about integrating people with other deep roots and memorial histories.

With German reunification, these debates have developed another layer of complexity. The experience of dictatorship, this time with state socialism, added to the question of how to deal with the past and what these multiple pasts now mean for the German social contract. A decisive layer of inequality was also added to the German social fabric through the specific nature of reunification, which was an incorporation of East Germany into the existing legal, political and economic structure of West Germany. Today's reunified Germany is confronted with a clash of very different memories that are deeply rooted, as well as vastly different cultures and politics of memory.

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Hungary

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Overview

Hungary, as the Kingdom of Hungary, was an independent entity from the 11th to the 16th century, mainly claiming allegiance to Western Christianity (Rome). This area was a borderland between different empires: the Ottoman Empire in the East and the Habsburg Empire in the West. There were also anti-feudal revolts. After 1526, Hungary split into three parts: one part fell under Ottoman rule; the Kingdom of Hungary became part of the Habsburg Empire; the Transylvanian part remained a relatively autonomous entity. By the end of the 17th century, the country was liberated from Ottoman rule and, under Habsburg rule, became part of this empire. In 1848, fights for independence began, but these had failed by 1849. In 1867, a compromise with the Austrian monarchy granted Hungary significant autonomy. In the decades that followed, there were also policies of governance of the wide territory left to be ruled from Budapest (for a historical overview, see e.g., Sugar-Hanák-Frank, 1990; Kontler, 2002; Romsics, 2017).

Towards the end of the 18th century, 'Hungarianisation' policies sought to establish Hungarian (*magyar*) as the *lingua franca* and language of governance in the multi-ethnic state (cf. Kontler, 2002; Nádor, 2002). The official language of the country throughout most of the previous centuries was Latin, while Hungarian, like the other languages of the country, functioned as a vernacular. From the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries on, a movement emerged that sought to make Hungarian the official language. The Hungarian estates first articulated this demand in opposition to the decree of the absolutist Habsburg monarch Joseph II, who had replaced Latin with German as the official language, in 1784. In the formation of national identity, language came to play a central role, especially in the first half of the 19th century. At the same time, in the multiethnic state, this led to tensions with the non-Hungarian speaking groups (Croatian, Slovak, Serb, Romanian, German, etc.). The Hungarian nation-building was thus an integration project with exclusions and a pressure of assimilation on minorities, which later became the source of conflicts. The empire's dissolution after WWI also led to the loss of two-thirds of Hungarian territory, resulting from the 1921 Treaty of Trianon in Paris. This also resulted in the loss of most of the minorities and contributed to the formation of an ethnically homogenous society. The former territory became parts of newly built or transformed states, such as Czechoslovakia, Romania and Yugoslavia. Plebiscites were held along the Hungarian-Austrian border to determine whether towns would join Austria or Hungary.

As a result of the Treaty of Trianon, Hungary lost two-thirds of its territory and mourning this lost land became an important part of the Hungarian memory (e.g., Feischmidt, 2020; Gyáni, 2012; Bálint et al., 2020). This memory translated to state practice with irredentist undertones. In 1949, Hungary became part of the Soviet Bloc. In summary, Hungary had a colonised history for much of its past. These 'national traumas', particularly in the 20th century, have played a significant role in national identity formation and are a driving force behind contemporary right-wing populist politics.

These past colonial and imperial experiences impacted national identity. A significant example is Hungary's national anthem itself, written in the early 19th century. The first verse speaks of a condition of being "long torn by ill fate" and how "This nation has suffered for all sins/Of the past and of the future". One can claim that this traumatic past is one of the fundamental layers of national mythology in Hungary. Authoritarianism also has had an impact on identity constructions; regarding the present political situation, the most important effect is on the right. The dismissal of the communist dictatorships of the 20th century became a key element of the identity of right-wing parties after 1990. Since the strongest left-wing party after the regime change was the successor to the former communist party, this strong rejection also extended to them, contributing to political polarisation. The Treaty of Trianon resulted in territorial loss, and a significant number of Hungarians became members of another state. This made the idea of the loss of a once-great nation a part of Hungary's right-wing/far-right mythology, bringing nostalgic feelings to the surface. This also implied the restoration of an original, ancient unity. The politics of constructing minority Hungarians living in neighbouring countries as a part of the Hungarian nation (e.g., by granting them citizenship) is a form of "national unification". This is one of the fundamental layers of the social contract constructed by the right (Fidesz).

After WWI, there was a short-lived experience of a Soviet Republic (21 March – 1 August 1919), led by Béla Kun. This was crushed and led to anti-communist legislation. During the interwar period, Hungary lived under authoritarian rule, led by Miklós Horthy, whose regime mirrored Mussolini's style more than Hitler's. There was the 'White Terror', a period of repressive violence against supporters of the Hungarian Soviet Republic (1919-1921), and pogroms in the countryside. Jewish people had an established position across the former Kingdom of Hungary, but in 1922, the first anti-Semitic legislation restricted Jewish students' access to universities. At the end of WWII, over half of the Jewish population of Hungary was sent to death camps as part of the Final Solution, under the fascist rule of the Hungarian Arrow Cross, which was eager to collaborate with Nazi Germany (Braham, 1994).

The country was liberated from Nazi rule on April 4, 1945. With a political takeover and Soviet troops stationed on its territory from 1949 to 1990, the country was placed under the Soviet

sphere of influence. This Stalinist period (Rákosi era) originated an uprising in 1956, followed by the consolidation of a moderate authoritarian (Kádár) regime that brought about a new social contract, based on economic prosperity at the expense of freedom of speech: the so-called *goulash communism*. As the system could not deliver economic prosperity even after the regime had been taking up IMF loans -- the first country in the Soviet Bloc to do so -- this contract started to crumble. The opposition rallied around the Helsinki Accords and the political liberties missing from the state socialist regime. They were also explicitly calling for a social contract in the 1980s. "The opposition had a great part in shaking the system of János Kádár, but the real breakthrough came with the since then famous document called *Társadalmi Szerződés* (Social Contract)" (Csizmadia, 2015, p. 129).

The ensuing transition was negotiated between the opposition groups and the powerholders, becoming the basis of the party system after the first free multiparty elections of 1990. A process of gradual integration into Euro-Atlantic organisations unfolded, resulting in Hungary's accession to NATO (late 1990s) and the EU (2004), in the so-called 'Big Bang' Enlargement. These elements of the Hungarian social contract were quite consensual, even if political polarisation started to emerge in the late 1990s, when Viktor Orbán's Fidesz accessed power. Thus, in the beginning, all parties agreed on the country's orientation towards Euro-Atlantic culture and its integration into the existing Euro-Atlantic institutions. Later, this started to change, and accelerated during Orbán's tenure from 2010, bringing harsh EU criticism, alongside a so-called eastern opening that included an openness towards both China and Russia. The reorientation of the country was a point of disagreement between the regime and its opposition and reinforced the pro-European and Western (versus Eastern) positioning in the opposition's political identity.

However, polarisation started to emerge significantly earlier and accelerated in the first Fidesz government between 1998 and 2002, and especially during the 2002 election campaign, becoming persistent after Fidesz came to power again in 2010. Even from the early phase of democratisation, the political landscape consisted of a deep suspicion of the political other in a process which led to a bipolar contestation (Palonen, 2009), and later illiberalism based on rejection of liberals as illegitimate to rule (Palonen, 2018).

After Orbán's Fidesz rose to power for the second time in 2010, the media and electoral laws were quickly changed. The EP resolution of 2022 considers the Orbán regime as an electoral autocracy (Delbos-Corfield, 2022), where elections take place, but with "a breakdown in democracy, the rule of law and fundamental rights". The public sphere is controlled to the extent that political change is very hard to achieve.

One of the most interesting problems regarding the current social contract is the continuity between the state socialist and Orbán's illiberal social contract. Our hypothesis is that this lies in consumption (see *goulash communism* above) and that theories of non-democratic social contracts can envisage this relation. These types of contracts enclose the equilibrium interaction between society and state; “the entirety of explicit or implicit agreements between all relevant societal groups and the sovereign” (Loewe et al., 2021, p. 3). The central question of the social contract here is why a society supports the government or a regime for a longer period and why such support ends. The social contract here encompasses the relationship between *state* and *society*, where the empirical question is which *provisions* both sides expect from each other, and how they fulfil them.

In the case of Hungary, relative prosperity is understood as a key deliverable for which a society is expected to support the government. Post-56 Kádárism's main provision was consumption, alongside a moderate welfare state (e.g., free health care and state housing programs). The fundamental social contract layer of the socialist regime appears to have been functioning effectively after the 2010 elections as well, in the form of a moderate yet persistent increase in average income until the early 2020s.

Further research is needed on the roles anti-authoritarianism and revolutionary rhetoric play in the polarisation that has strengthened since the early 2000s. It is still necessary to understand how these factors contribute to the emergence of the post-democratic Orbán regime and their articulation with the current social contract in Hungary. One of the leading identity-forming problems of the democratic era, following the 1990s regime change, is the country's relation to 'communism' (e.g., for Fidesz). Additionally, further investigation is required about how a new political force (Tisza Party), which is currently challenging the regime, is rewriting these elements and shaping the framework of a new social contract as a political offer for the future.

Political, social and economic inequalities

In Hungary, deep social and economic divides shape the lived experiences of its people. Women, for instance, face stark inequalities, both in earnings and political representation. As of 2023, women earn on average 17.3% less than men – a percentage well above the EU's average of 12.7% (Európai Parlament, 2023). Women's voices in politics are similarly limited; as of 2025, only about 15% of parliamentary seats are held by women, while not a single woman is part of the government or among the nation's top leaders (Members of Parliament 2025).

Ethnic diversity also remains a fraught issue. Hungary's demographic makeup was profoundly altered after WWI, when the country lost much of its territory, significantly reducing its ethnic diversity. Today, the Roma represent the largest national minority, with 2.5% of the population officially identifying as such in the 2022 census (Központi Statisztikai Hivatal, 2022a, b). However, systemic discrimination is likely to have led to underreporting, with estimates suggesting the actual figure is closer to 5-10% (Pénzes et al., 2024). The Roma community – and especially Roma women – faces persistent economic hardship, with limited access to stable employment and higher poverty rates. Information from Hungary's national statistical office's homepage shows the difference between the employment rate of the Roma and non-Roma population (as of 2022), for example. <https://ksh.hu/s/kiadvanyok/fenntarthato-fejlodes-indikatorai-2022/4-2> These data also show that a significant number of Roma employees only work as engaged in the state-funded scheme, and not on the free job market. Within this marginalised group, further divisions exist, adding layers of complexity to their struggle for equal rights.

Geographically, Hungary is a nation of sharp contrasts. Budapest stands as the country's economic powerhouse, its GDP soaring to approximately 150% of the EU average. In stark contrast, rural areas lag, with economic output hovering at just 50-70% of the EU average. Wages in the countryside are significantly lower, by as much as 20-40%, creating a widening gap in opportunities and quality of life (Központi Statisztikai Hivatal, 2022b). This capital-city versus the rest of the country's territory divide has long been a structural feature of Hungary's economy, reinforcing regional disparities in wealth, services and political influence.

Environmental concerns have also ignited tensions in recent years. The government's push for foreign battery factories has triggered local resistance, echoing the environmental protests of the 1980s and the renewed wave of ecological activism of the late 2000s. These conflicts reflect broader anxieties about industrial expansion and its impact on communities, already struggling with economic and social inequalities (on the expansion of EV battery industry in Hungary, cf. Gyórfy 2023, 2024).

Against this backdrop, questions emerge about the foundations of Hungary's current social contract. Under Viktor Orbán's rule, the government appears to rely on implicit exclusions – particularly of women and Roma – while drawing political support from rural communities. With legislation that restricts the rights of people belonging to the LGBTQI community, and the powerful discursive constructions against them, the government explicitly excludes citizens from the social contract. Yet, these exclusions and fractures in Hungarian society could also provide fertile ground for an alternative, counter-hegemonic vision of democracy. As the legitimacy of the existing consumerist model faces increasing strain, the question remains as

to whether these social divides can be mended or if they will continue to define Hungary's path.

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Portugal

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Overview

The constitution of Portugal as an autonomous political entity was an evolving process and dates to the 12th century. Some events – often seen as foundational myths, due to the lack of abundant historical documentation and the way some nationalist historians have interpreted them in the past – can be listed as milestones, such as the Battle of Ourique, in 1139, where Afonso Henriques proclaimed himself King of Portugal, or the “Treaty” of Zamora (1143). The last constituted a diplomatic meeting during which D. Afonso VII (King of León, Castile and Galicia) seemed to have recognised D. Afonso Henriques as the King of Portugal. However, full sovereignty (considering the system of powers in place Europe during the Middle Age that conferred such type of authority to the Holy See) would only be confirmed later, in 1179, by the papal bull ‘Manifestis probatum’ (see, among others: Branco, 2015; Mattoso, 2021; Mattoso & Sousa, 1993). Since then, founding features of the Portuguese social contract began to emerge, including: Portugal’s peripheral location in Europe; historical external relations, in particular with Spain (mostly with the Kingdom of Castile until Spain’s unification in the late 15th century), England and France; or the edification of the first and long-lasting modern overseas colonial Empire.

Relations with the Holy See and Christianity are also constitutive of Portugal’s social contract. As the state’s religion, Christianity deeply influenced the forging of Portugal’s national identity, shaping several dimensions of the country’s individual and collective lives for centuries. Whereas the Holy See played an important role in the recognition of its independence, Portugal also was pivotal to reinforcing the Catholic Church’s power and geographical influence. This happened a few centuries before Portuguese colonialism has contributed to spreading the influence of the Catholic Church to other regions of the world. As one of the Iberian Christian kingdoms, from the mid-12th century to the mid-13th century Portugal engaged in several wars. Generally referred to as *Reconquista*, these conflicts aimed at both expanding its territory and ending Muslim domination in the southern Peninsula. This complex process, marked by advances and setbacks, was concluded in 1249 with the conquest of Algarve, the southernmost region of continental Portugal. After the expulsion of the last Muslim establishment in the Algarve, Portugal’s mainland territorial borders were defined and, with minor adjustments, have remained the same ever since.

Portugal's identity as the oldest European nation-state is sustained by myths associated with an independence forged in the 12th century, the establishment of the oldest territorial borders in Europe and the population's linguistic and religious homogeneity. Such a narrative fuels public and cultural imaginaries about nationhood to this day (Branco, 2015; Herculano, 2007; João, 2022; Sobral, 2006).

Notwithstanding, during the Middle Ages, Muslim and Jewish minorities were granted royal protection, allowing them to be integrated in a "pluralistic [Portuguese] society" (Soyer, 2008, p. 215). However, as Christianity was reinforced as a constitutive element of Portugal's identity, by the late 15th century, a more exclusionary approach became dominant, whereby Muslims and Jews were persecuted, expelled or forced to convert to Christianity. At this point, religion and the support of the Holy See became constitutive elements of Portuguese colonialism and its triple goals: territorial expansion, economic growth and the spread of Christianity.

The occupation of Ceuta (North Africa) in 1415, marked the beginning of Portugal's overseas imperialism, which unfolded in the following decades with the exploration of the African coast and the establishment of commercial maritime routes to India. The evolution of the social contract in Portugal is, thus, historically intertwined with the country's imperial composition. Since the Modern Era, important official documents framed its legal-political structure and social regulation. Namely, the privileges, freedoms and duties of the three estates (clergy, nobility and commoners) established a pluricontinental configuration of the then-Portuguese Monarchy. Historical events triggering ruptures in the prevailing political and social order were also nodal points, reinforcing the link between colonialism and the social contract.³

Portugal's institutional organisation and social contract are therefore built upon an imperial framework, progressively reinforced from the late 19th century until the end of the Empire (about a century later). Starting in 1870, processes of *imperialisation of the nation* were consolidated as "the empire (re)affirmed itself as a fundamental symbolic and cultural resource

³ Portugal's most relevant constitutional texts include: the charter that King Philip II of Spain (I of Portugal) granted to Portugal at the assembly courts convened in Tomar in 1581, sanctioning the Dynastic Union between Spain and Portugal (1580-1640); the Constitution of 1822 – the first (liberal) Portuguese constitution, promulgated following the Liberal Revolution of 1820, which ended the Ancient Regime and established the Constitutional Monarchy; the Constitutional Charter of 1826; the Constitution of 1838; the (republican) Constitution of 1911; the Constitution of 1933, formally establishing the Estado Novo; the Constitution of 1976, currently into force.

for the (re)formulation of national identity and as a political and economic instrument for the desired national regeneration” (Jerónimo, 2015, p. 109-110). To underpin this project, the empire conveyed *civilizing mission* doctrines, stressing its historical colonising mission and imposing ideas of western civilizational superiority, as well as a notion of *imperial exceptionalism* (Jerónimo, 2015, p. 110). However, during the *Estado Novo* (New State) (1933-1974) this process was further consolidated by the regime’s propaganda and ideological inculcation apparatus (Cardina, 2023, p. 33-46; Peralta, 2011, p. 205-209; Rosas, 2015, p. 328-341).

Over the last 50 years, the social contract in Portugal has undergone major adjustments because of deep endogenous and exogenous political, economic, social and cultural changes. The end of the *Estado Novo* and colonial empire (1974), as well as the establishment of democracy and European integration (1986), were major historical processes that led to new developments and impacted the current social contract.

The circumstances in which the transition from dictatorship to democracy took place led to abrupt changes in all areas of collective life and the social contract. This transition was marked simultaneously by: 1) a revolutionary process; 2) the end of the Portuguese Colonial War (1961-1974); 3) a decolonisation process resulting in the independence of five countries in Africa and the migration of around 500,000 people to Portugal (according to conservative estimates), mostly white settlers living in Angola and Mozambique (Pires, 2003, p. 199-200); 4) the democratic consolidation process under strong military tutelage, performed by the *Movimento das Forças Armadas* (MFA – Armed Forces Movement), the driving force of the 25th of April coup that overthrew the *Estado Novo* in 1974.

The MFA military coup received widespread popular support and was followed by the *Processo Revolucionário em Curso* [PREC – Ongoing Revolutionary Process]. This was an intense period characterised by socialist and collective power experiments, including: worker occupations of factories, large rural properties and inhabited urban properties; industrial and business self-management; participatory practices, such as literacy campaigns or housing cooperatives. It was also marked by military coups and countercoups; land occupation and the organisation of collective production units, with the Agrarian Reform as the final goal; the nationalisation of banks, large companies and strategic sectors of the economy; purges of employers, administrations, diplomats and high-ranking officials of the deposed regime. The direction of this revolutionary period was uncertain until November 25, 1975, but it eventually converged to stabilise Portugal as a liberal representative democracy. Democratisation was established with the approval of the 1976 Constitution, along with the first free presidential, legislative and local elections that same year, thus putting an end to PREC (for an overview

on these processes, see among others: Pinto, 2001; Rezola, 2023, 2006; Rosas, 2020; Ruivo, 2015; Spognardi, 2019; Varela, 2014; 50anos25abril).

The 25th of April enabled the enshrinement of fundamental freedoms and guarantees, as well as political, economic, cultural and social rights. Political prisoners were released two days after the coup, heralding the right to freedom of expression. For the first time in Portugal, the 1975 Press Law did not envisage any kind of censorship. Additionally, the rights to strike and vacation were guaranteed, working hours were reduced and a minimum wage was established. These rights resulted from popular mobilisation, as well as disputes and negotiations between various political and military actors running the country during PREC, thus emerging as a “popular conquest imposed on power” (Rosas, 2020, p. 70).

The April Revolution enabled changes in the legal system, aiming at guaranteeing full equality between men and women. Women were legally granted full access to vote and autonomy in all spheres of life. During the *Estado Novo*, married women needed their husband’s permission to work or travel abroad, while nurses and flight attendants were not allowed to marry. After the Carnation Revolution (1974), women could access jobs that were previously interdicted, conquering the possibility of becoming judges, diplomats or the police. Divorce, previously banned for catholic marriages by the 1940 *Concordata* (international treaty) signed between Portugal and the Holy See, became possible under decree-law no. 261/75 (known as the ‘new divorce law’). However, disparities in terms of access and opportunities in the social, economic and political spheres continued to shape women’s lives. In practice, gender inequality weighs heavily on public and professional life, as well as in the domestic sphere. It is noticeable in wage asymmetries between men and women; job segregation; greater fragility in terms of social protection, since women tend to work more in the informal economy; overwhelming domestic work and care provision (Peniche, 2020, p. 251).

Overall, Portuguese decolonisation and democratisation are thus characterised by their radical and revolutionary dimensions (Loff, 2014). The political turmoil involved in both processes implied deep social and economic changes, including the constitution of the country’s welfare state’s basic pillars. Namely, these pillars included: the creation of the National Health Service that granted access to essential medical care to all citizens; the extension and democratisation of the public education system; the establishment of a public social security system, integrating all, even those with no previous social security contributions. The progressive expansion of the welfare state, societal-oriented public policies and public investment had a significant impact on the amelioration of living conditions. The quality of life of the Portuguese population improved, particularly for the lower and middle classes.

However, the end of the Portuguese Empire was not accompanied by the disappearance of imperial mythologies disseminated in the public sphere. Instead, they were adapted to reflect Portugal's transformation from a colonial power to a semi-peripheral country. In many cases these mythologies were reinforced, as Portugal redefined its geopolitical position and advanced in the process of European integration. Likewise, the memory of the colonial past continued to influence, for instance: conceptions and narratives about history and national identity, namely as rhetoric for promoting the country and the Portuguese people internationally; official speeches about the nation; Portugal's geopolitical vision and diplomacy; cultural and literary production (to further explore about this topic we suggest, among others, the following readings: Cardim, 2023; Cardina, 2023; Peralta, 2011; Pinto & Jerónimo, 2015; Sidaway & Power, 2005).

Political, social and economic inequalities

Historically, colonialism generated distinct migration flows within the imperial space – white settlers, enslaved people, colonial administrators and civil servants, military personnel, people subjected to forced labour, among others –, thus creating regimes of oppression and differentiation, and generating manifold exclusions. Those are articulated with socio-economic inequalities, mainly in terms of access to employment and the labour market, as well as in access to decent housing, education, justice and healthcare, faced by people from the former colonized territories coming to Portugal in the decades following decolonization. These populations were, and still are, also subjected to several forms of discrimination such as structural racism, xenophobia and police violence (see, among others: Raposo et al., 2019; Vala, Brito & Lopes, 1999).

If this history still impacts on those populations' everyday life, the articulation of the Colonial Past memory in Portugal – characterized by the enduring influence of the *lusotropicalism* and Portuguese *exceptionalism* ideologies – fuels discussions about multiculturalism and creates misperceptions about their integration and the prejudices they face. Lusotropicalism was an idea developed by Brazilian sociologist Gilberto Freyre, who postulated the unique characteristics of the Portuguese people to intermingle and interact harmoniously with the peoples and cultures of the tropics. The main ones were the absence of racial prejudice, the promotion of miscegenation, and fraternal Christianity (Castelo, 1998, p. 33). This 'theory' posited that Portuguese colonialism was more benign than other European colonialisms, leading to its appropriation by the Estado Novo as a vector to sustain the continuity of the Empire in a world marked by the winds of decolonization. In addition to the regime's elites, the Lusotropicalist ideology was widely disseminated in mass culture during the last decades of

the dictatorship (Castelo, 1999; Cardão, 2014). Its reverberations extend to the present day (Almeida, 2000).

The factors for Portugal's lower economic performance, compared with other territories in central and northern Europe, have been intensely discussed and analysed.⁴ The following have been pointed out: the country's peripheral situation; low population; aggravated by the migratory movements resulting from colonial exploitation; poor agricultural soils and the lack of major natural resources underground; the 1703 Methuen Treaty with Great Britain, which arguably resulted in unfavourable trade relations and prevented the development of the manufacturing industry; late and meagre industrial development; and the insufficient modernisation of agriculture, which remains largely based on family farming models and smallholdings, especially in the central and northern regions.

At the end of the 19th century, a group of historians and thinkers (e.g., Antero de Quental) identified the main causes for the decline of Iberian countries from the 17th century onwards: Catholicism, the Counter-Reformation and the Inquisition, political centralisation established by the Absolute Monarchy and an economic system contingent upon colonial exploitation (Quental, 2022).

At different times, historians and economists have questioned the cost-benefit ratio of the colonies. Some have hypothesised that colonial trade and the wealth it generated, as well as the human resources required by colonial exploitation, prevented an efficient use of the Portuguese territory and its economic development.⁵ However, in addition to being disputed, these macroeconomic perspectives do not consider that the Empire – whether in terms of natural resources and local workforce exploitation, or as a market for national exports – was an important source of wealth for various economic agents, both in Portugal and overseas. The link between the national economy and colonial exploitation influenced the expectations and decisions made by settlers, entrepreneurs, families and firms, ultimately guiding the development of the Portuguese economy.

In addition to the economic question, the political (and symbolic) dimensions of maintaining the colonies were also decisive for various political regimes (the Absolutism, Constitutional Monarchy, First Republic and particularly *Estado Novo*, in the final phase of colonialism).

⁴ See also, e.g.: Amaral, 2024, p. 169-180; Ferreira, 2005; Lains, 1998; Lourenço, 2007; Murteira, 1998; Palma, 2024; Quental, 2022; Santos, 1996, p. 49-67.

⁵ See also, e.g.: Lains, 1998; Louçã, 2020, p. 152; Palma, 2024; Pereira, 2012.

Colonial rule influenced the definition of national policy and politics, as well as the survival of the regimes themselves. Over the 14 years of the Colonial War, the average expenditure on the Armed Forces in relation to total state spending was 30% (Sousa, 2021, p. 261). In effect, sustaining the war effort drained funds that could have been earmarked for social policies, public services (namely education and health), building and modernising infrastructure, as well as developing the economy.

In sum, the continuous renegotiation of the social contract in Portugal, therefore, points to a complex process at the intersection of relations with the Holy See, imperialism, colonialism and authoritarianism. Together, these elements provide valuable insights to understand the deep roots of persisting political, social and economic inequalities. More recently, the Carnation Revolution (1974) and Portugal's European integration (1986) have decisively shaped the current social contract through significant transformations in the political, economic and social landscape.

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Sweden

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Overview

Long before the notion of colonial empires took firm root in Europe, Sweden had already established itself as a regional power during the hundred years of its so-called *stormaktstiden* (the Swedish Empire, 1611-1721). The country had different state unions and complicated relations with neighbouring powers, with the present area of Finland being an integral part of Sweden, lacking its own administrative structures or linguistic autonomy. Whether this constituted colonialism or mere hegemony remains an ongoing discussion (in Finland, see Keskinen 2019). During this time, the people indigenous to the Sápmi cultural region were regularly discriminated against in all the countries they inhabited (Norway, Finland, Sweden and Russia). During the 19th century, they were targeted by forced cultural assimilation and Christianisation. In the 20th century, due to the popularity of racial hygiene ideas in Sweden, both the Sámi people and Finns were racialised. The debates on these measures and practices, as well as their consequences, continue in contemporary Sweden.

Sweden's foray into overseas colonialism, though very limited in extent and time (1638-1663 and 1784-1878), was also initiated during the Empire era. The kingdom held small colonies in Africa, Asia and the Americas, the most notable one being the island of Saint Barthélemy in the Caribbean. Here, Sweden actively participated in the transatlantic slave trade, a dark chapter in its history that lasted until the island was sold to France in 1878, officially marking the end of Sweden's colonial ambitions (for more of this history, see e.g. Naum & Nordin 2013).

After the Empire era, Sweden remained a regional power until the 1809 Finnish war, when Russia invaded Finland, which consequently became a Grand Duchy within Imperial Russia. It was also gradually forced to relinquish its power over Norway, which had been a part of Sweden or Denmark (or both) in varying constellations for centuries. Norway declared independence in 1905. Sweden remained out of both the world wars, declaring a neutrality policy. In the 19th century, the country became increasingly democratic, with a parliamentary representative constitutional monarchy already in practice by 1917. In the early 20th century, Sweden transitioned from an agricultural to an urban, industrial society, becoming an economically successful producer of steel and new technology.

Since its establishment in 1889, the Social Democratic Workers Party swiftly grew in power, quickly becoming the country's biggest party. It held almost uncontested power in Sweden

throughout the 20th century, a period when their ideological tenets (a mixture of practical Marxism, liberalism and egalitarianism) defined Swedish politics. In the latter half of the 20th century, Sweden saw the rise of the Social Democratic Party, with their ideological project of *folkhemmet* (the home of the people) and grounded on strong human rights movements. Sweden has often presented itself as a progressive beacon of human rights, while distinguishing itself as a vocal critic of oppressive post-colonial regimes. For example, it took a strong stance against apartheid in South Africa and denounced American involvement in the Vietnam War. For decades, Sweden cultivated a self-image as a “superpower of human rights,” but in today’s political climate, this title has been increasingly questioned and even ridiculed, both at home and abroad.

Only recently has Sweden started to account for its own colonial activities, as well as the treatment of the Sámi people and the institutionalised racial hygiene in the first half of the 20th century. The great narrative of a progressive nation is now countered with a less tidy narrative of a racially and ethnically exclusive, monocultural nation (see e.g. Eriksen et al., 2019).

Before the era of democratisation, Sweden was ruled by a succession of hereditary kings. Their powers were already diminished considerably over the 18th century, after the Swedish Empire came to an end. While Sweden remains a constitutional monarchy, it has been a democratic nation since 1921, the year universal suffrage was established. Its early embrace of press freedom set a precedent for democratic values, with the 1766 Swedish Freedom of the Press Act recognised as the first of its kind (Nordin et al., 2023). The 19th century was a time of rising democratisation, while the simultaneous counter-narrative involved elites ruling an increasingly monocultural country. However, Sweden had a powerful upper class, including a nobility which, while greatly weakened, was still enjoying some hereditary privileges. This tendency continued into 20th century, when Sweden was industrially successful, growing and absorbing hundreds of thousands of immigrants in the 1970s. At first, the majority came from Finland, which was still grappling with the economic consequences of the war, having been attacked by the Soviet Union in 1939. People also arrived from Italy, former Yugoslavia and Middle Eastern countries.

The political ideal had been that of consensus and mutual trust in a society, where all the citizens know and follow the rather strict rules of the monoethnic social contract. These values were inherited from the previous agrarian society, starkly contradicting the modern, multicultural, urban society in formation. The newcomers challenged the previous truisms of the Swedish nation, while frequently stigmatised and driven into a new underclass. There was also a racial undertone in this stigmatisation, regardless of the official rhetoric emphasizing the *folkhemmet* ideology. (McEachrane, 2024)

Presently, the members of the former ruling classes, powerful families and nobility remain overrepresented in the boards of big companies, as well as in politics, and at the head of cultural institutions. This gives the Swedish social contract an interesting duality, where it is simultaneously aiming for the appearance of equal opportunities, while maintaining traces of the ancient social divisions. Due to unsuccessful integration policies and an increasingly segregated society, Sweden now grapples with rising gang related crime and violence. In response to this, the nation has gradually tightened legislation and expanded police authority, shifting towards a more authoritarian stance to restore order. The present political discussions and interventions favour law-and-order policies. Several cases exemplify these trends. For example, in the spring of 2025, tighter laws were set for those under 15 years of age, suspected of crimes, which has been a subject of lively discussion (Sveriges Radio, 2025). There is also currently a motion from the government to lower the limit of criminal responsibility to 14 years of age for serious crimes. Additionally, the government is building new youth prisons, which will expectedly open in 2026. These examples show that the country currently finds itself at a crossroads between balancing its historical identity as a bastion of human rights with the pressing demands of domestic security.

With regards to international security, Sweden is now a part of NATO. While after the WW2 it used to have official policy of neutrality, it was nevertheless clandestinely working with the NATO. It also discontinued the mandatory military service in the 1990s. Now, conscription has not yet been properly reintroduced, but in the future it might set challenges to the social contract. The recent adhesion to NATO was an enormous, and not unanimously popular step. However, in the public and private discussions, there is a general sense of regret of the earlier demilitarisation. Therefore, it is difficult to predict, whether this will really impact the social contract, as joining NATO will also increase the sense of security in Sweden.

Political, social and economic inequalities

Overall, the gradual crumbling of the Swedish welfare state, its failure to accommodate immigrant populations and persistent ethno-racial segregation have led to societal and political tensions. Inequalities in Sweden have long been low for European standards, but it is still worth noting that the country's comparatively low Gini Coefficient has been rising steadily over the last 20 years, with Sweden now topping the Nordic countries. In addition, Swedish cities are now among the most residentially segregated in Europe (Thörn & Thörn, 2017).

Sweden remains a high-income country and is still a very resilient society. However, increasing inequality together with persistently high segregation has alarmed social discussants, while crumbling the Swedish self-image as one of the most equal countries in the

world (Calmfors & Roine, 2018; Nordregio, 2020). Finally, environmental awareness is high in Sweden, as shown, for example, by the success of the Swedish Green Party in the EU elections of 2024. Sweden has been traditionally ranked highly in the UN sustainable development reports (UN, 2024), although some challenges remain. For example, in a 2025 report, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), while acknowledging the progressive climate politics, also heavily criticised the Swedish climate policies for cutting fuel tax rates and the loss of biodiversity (OECD, 2025).

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Türkiye

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Overview

Türkiye is a bridge across troubled lands (Kalaycioğlu, 2005) and is “in-between” West and East; Europe and Asia; “developed” and “developing” countries (Karatay et al., 2016). Türkiye’s relationship with Europe, particularly with the EU, has also been a long journey of struggle. Türkiye, a member of the Council of Europe since 1950, has been a candidate for full EU membership since December 1999; however, Türkiye’s accession process still seems far from being materialised. However, how Türkiye was/has been regarded by the people/societies of Europe and how people in Türkiye have perceived Europe is of utmost relevance for a discussion on the country’s social contract, which is deeply rooted in historical developments (Yapp, 1992).

Both European and Ottoman/Turkish views of each other have traditionally been hard to portray. The challenging question of whether Türkiye, as a country with a small part of land on the European continent, has ever truly been a part of Europe remains unanswered. The relationship between the Ottoman Empire and Europe was shaped by evolving mutual identity representations, particularly between the French Revolution (1789) and establishment of the Turkish Republic (1923) (Aydın-Düzgüt, Chovanec & Rumelili, 2021; Gocek, 2007). European views of the Ottomans shifted from seeing them as a threatening power to a “sick man” (Çırakman, 2005). Over time, the Ottoman Empire had to grant trade privileges to European powers through multiple capitulations, which allowed European merchants to trade and travel within Ottoman dominions under their own laws. For Ottoman elites, Westernisation, and mainly Europe, was a model of civilisation and progress (Mardin, 1962). In this light, the Ottoman Empire initiated various reforms, most notably during the Tanzimat period (1839-1876), to modernise its military, bureaucracy and legal systems driven by the need to compete with European powers. However, the rise of Turkism in the early Republican period (1920s and 1930s) led to a distinction between ‘civilisation’, which refers to progress, and ‘culture’, meaning national identity combined with religion.

The Ottoman Empire's relationship with Europe regarding colonialism is complex and cannot be fully understood through the lens of traditional European colonialism (Türesay, 2013; Topal, 2020). While the Ottomans did not engage in overseas colonisation like European powers, their interactions and internal dynamics reveal a complex picture with elements that some scholars have termed ‘Ottoman colonialism’. These scholars argue that by the late 19th and

early 20th centuries, the Ottoman elite had begun to adopt a European-style imperialist mindset, creating a discourse of difference between the imperial centre and the peripheral provinces, particularly in Arab regions. This 'Ottoman orientalism' was characterised by a hierarchical view, associating the centre with modernity and civilisation, contrasting with the backwardness and tradition of the periphery (Makdisi, 2002; Eldem 2015). The Ottoman Empire aimed for administrative centralisation and integrated its provinces into the political system. The Ottoman state was more concerned with internal control and consolidation, rather than overseas colonial expansion, as part of traditional imperial practices of differentiation. The Ottoman Empire did not have colonies, and its African policies have been described as 'borrowed colonialism' (Deringil, 2003). 'Defensive imperialism' is another term that explains the Ottoman Empire's attitude, as a contracting empire trying to survive against expanding European powers (Ülker, 2021).

The enduring influence of the Ottoman Empire on Turkish politics is a crucial factor in understanding the roots of authoritarianism in the country. According to Heper (1985, 1992), the legacy of the Ottoman Empire in the Republic of Türkiye relies on the transcendental state. He emphasises that the bureaucratic elites continued to embrace the transcendental state as indispensable for keeping the community unified and 'saving the State' also in the Republican era. From this perspective, Heper (2000) argues that the defining characteristic of Turkish political culture is continuity rather than change. Specifically, he highlights the powerful tradition of a centralised state, the prominent role of the military and the absence of a robust civil society producing policies along with a strong state (*ibid.*). Despite Türkiye's formal democratisation following WWII, the military has since intervened in politics multiple times, complicating the country's democratic trajectory. Turan (2015) captures this struggle in his work, aptly subtitled 'Two Steps Forward, One Step Back'.

Zürcher (2004) emphasises the role of non-democratic and authoritarian actors and policies in shaping the political landscape. In the early years of the republic, Turkish politics were characterised by an acknowledgment of their single-party authoritarian nature. Over time, discussions increasingly focused on the hopes and shortcomings of democratisation, with a growing emphasis on various authoritarian features, rather than on an institutionalised authoritarian regime. The Justice and Development Party (AKP), which ascended to power in 2002, initially sought to implement reforms aimed at strengthening Türkiye's fragile democracy, while exploiting state resources (Yavuz, 2023). However, since the 2010s, many observers have perceived a renewed assault on democratic principles. This assault is marked by the erosion of checks and balances, a disregard for the rule of law, a crackdown on the media, the suppression of the judiciary and civil society, as well as the utilisation of anti-terror laws to suppress dissent.

The failed coup of 15th of July 2016 precipitated the declaration of a state of emergency, which led to constitutional changes that fostered a more centralised presidential system. Studies on the AKP are particularly noteworthy for their periodisation, as initial assessments concentrated on the party's democratisation efforts, while later analyses have shifted to examine its authoritarian turn (İnsel, 2003; Esen and Gümüşçü, 2016; Esen, 2022; Yavuz, 2023). Central to this discourse are the roles of the military, political Islam, the Kurdish question, uneven economic development and the status of women within the context of Turkish political dynamics.

Political, social and economic inequalities

The relationship between political, social and economic disparities, as well as environmental factors in Türkiye is intricate, with historical roots tracing back to the Ottoman period and the formation of the Republic. The Ottoman Empire implemented the 'millet system' to manage its various religious communities, which reflects Türkiye's significant cultural diversity through its ethnic, religious and linguistic groups. Since the Lausanne Treaty (1923), certain groups, such as Armenians, Greeks and Jews, have been primarily recognised as minorities. Additionally, Kurds and Alevi also contribute to the diverse fabric of the country.

The formation of the republic and the drivers of nation-building focused on a Turkish-Muslim identity, which often ended up excluding non-Muslim minorities. This process included Turkification policies that sought to unify the population through a common language and religion. In light of Türkiye's candidacy for EU membership, there were improvements in minority rights and in the recognition of the country's cultural diversity. Nevertheless, the influence of Turkish-Islamic heritage continues to shape the socio-political landscape of the country (İçduygu et al., 2008; Kaya & Baldwin, 2004).

Historically, the political climate has included a longstanding issue regarding the Kurdish population, commonly referred to as the 'Kurdish question'. This issue has been shaped by state policies, the Kurds' demands for cultural rights, the region's perceived backwardness, security concerns and geopolitical factors. According to Yeğen (2015, p. 3), the "Kurdish question" has been linked to three main elements resulting from state policies: assimilation, repression and containment (between 1923 and the 1990s). This period witnessed various Kurdish responses to assimilation policies, which included discrimination, displacement and violence. There has also been an armed struggle between the Kurdistan Workers' Party (PKK), a Kurdish militant political organisation, and the Turkish military. Additionally, this

period also saw the emergence of pro-Kurdish political parties participating in national elections.

Since 2009, the AKP government has introduced new initiatives to address the Kurdish question, emphasising an attempt towards a 'resolution/peace process'. This effort included negotiations with the PKK and implementing reforms, aimed at democratisation and recognising the cultural and political rights of Kurds, which continued until 2015 (Yeğen, 2023) and appears to recently show signs of revitalisation.

According to the Turkish Statistical Institute, Türkiye, home to 85 million people and ranked 17th in global economic size, faces significant challenges, ranking among the worst OECD countries in terms of child poverty rates. This context offers valuable insights into societal conflicts and inequalities, including income distribution, health, education and employment. Furthermore, the country's regional differences are vast (Karatay et al., 2016) and were multiplied by the earthquakes of February 2023. The country also hosts one of the biggest refugee and migrant populations, including more than 3.1 million Syrian refugees (Erdoğan and Uyan-Semerci, 2019). Vulnerable populations are disproportionately affected by the consequences of climate change, which exacerbates existing inequalities (Turhan et al., 2016). One significant risk associated with climate change is the potential for mass migration, as climate refugees face various interconnected challenges.

Türkiye, located in the Mediterranean Basin, is particularly at risk from the impacts of climate change. There are some rising temperatures in the region and the emergence of risks in providing water needs, leading to scarcity. According to the World Economic Forum, the economic effects of these environmental risks are expected to increase after 2030, presenting a vital opportunity for Türkiye to integrate its social policies with strategies aimed at mitigating climate change. Recognised as a significant social threat, climate change necessitates effective social policies to address its repercussions. However, Türkiye's current social policy frameworks might not be sufficiently equipped to confront the challenges posed by climate change, with possible sweeping effects for the country's social contract. The drive for economic growth, which supports the sustainability of social initiatives, often comes into conflict with the imperative of environmental sustainability.

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Ukraine

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Overview

In the Ukrainian context, the idea of a social contract is particularly complex and multidimensional. It was formed under the influence of external domination (imperial/colonial and authoritarian), which largely determined the nature of its political institutions, value systems and cultural codes. The colonial subordination of Ukrainian territories to various empires, and later to Soviet totalitarianism, led to the entrenchment of a paternalistic model of relations between citizens and the state. Thereby, the state was perceived as an all-powerful guardian, while civic participation was considered secondary or even dangerous.

This historical experience led to profound structural deformations in the country's culture of interaction between the state and society, which persisted in the first decades of independence. At the same time, since the beginning of the 21st century, Ukraine has witnessed a gradual, but decisive reconsideration regarding the foundations of this arrangement. This process became particularly evident after two major social upheavals: the Revolution of Dignity (2013-2014) and the full-scale Russian invasion in 2022. These events were not only political uprisings, but also profound acts revising the role of the citizens, the nature of state legitimacy and the principles of living in freedom, security and justice. Under the pressure of war and crisis, a new version of the social contract is emerging. No longer based on subordination and paternalism, this social contract is founded on mutual responsibility, dignity, horizontal solidarity and conscious citizenship. Contemporary Ukraine is in a state of complex transformation: on the one hand, it is forced to overcome the centuries-old continuity of imperial and authoritarian structures; on the other hand, it is actively shaping new social and political practices. The Ukrainian social contract is thus at the intersection of historical legacy and future design.

The social contract in Ukraine is deeply rooted in the historical experience of being under the rule of empires – Russian, Austro-Hungarian and, partly, Ottoman. The conditions of Ukrainian territories within these states shaped a particular political culture, a system of legal relations and an idea of the citizen's role in society. This historical experience has led to the asymmetric development of political culture in different regions, creating structural inequalities in state-society relations (Plokyh, 2016a).

The Russian Empire, and later the Soviet Union, reproduced a model in which citizens were perceived as objects of state control rather than as subjects. In such a system, state power

was not seen as serving the public good, but as a bearer of power for its own – and elites' - sake. At the same time, citizens deprived of legal personality were excluded from political participation. All this created a deep institutional and value gap between the state and society (Tucker, 1987).

The situation was quite different in the parts of Ukraine that were under the rule of the Austro-Hungarian Empire. There was a system of limited self-government, parliamentarism and political representation. Civic institutions – such as educational societies, cooperatives and trade unions – acted as a sort of citizenship school. The influence of the Greek Catholic Church also contributed to the preservation of national identity, developing a social ethos of responsibility and solidarity. This experience became the basis for the formation of a distinctive political culture in western Ukraine (Hrytsak, 2015).

By contrast, in the eastern and southern regions, the rule of the Russian Empire was dominated by other models – hierarchical, centralised, with minimal citizen participation in public life. The imperial administration systematically destroyed local self-government and eliminated autonomous structures. After the abolition of the Ukrainian Cossack State, (Hetmanate, 1649-1764), the tradition of Cossack political subjectivity was ultimately destroyed. Later, in the Soviet period, this led to the complete dominance of the vertical model of governance, in which the main function of a citizen was to follow directives from above and be loyal to the state ideology (Plokyh, 2016b).

Imperial politicians also used various instruments of cultural assimilation, repression and censorship. The effects of Russification, both of language and identity, were particularly noticeable. In the post-Soviet period, these narratives have been revived in the form of political struggles over language, historical memory and geopolitical orientation, reflecting the continuity of imperial mechanisms of influence. Thus, the formation of a modern social contract is impossible without understanding and overcoming the colonial legacy in the structure of Ukrainian statehood (Kulyk, 2018).

After gaining independence in 1991, Ukraine entered a new era of political and institutional development, but it did so with an authoritarian and paternalistic model of state governance inherited from the Soviet system. According to Mark Beissinger (2017), the Soviet social contract was based on the principle of “the state as the guarantor of stability, the citizen as a passive consumer of benefits”. This model did not envisage the active participation of citizens in decision-making processes; instead, the image prevailed of a 'silent majority' relying on the state as the sole source of security, services and social care.

This paternalistic approach led to social inertia, a low level of political culture, alienation from institutions and weak political subjectivity among citizens. In the early years of independence,

this was reflected in the indifference of a large part of the population to democratic processes. Furthermore, the state administration retained the characteristics of a command-and-control system. Citizens did not see themselves as active participants in the social contract, but rather as beneficiaries of services provided by the state within the old logic of 'social exchange' (Bertelsen, 2017; Tucker, 1987).

Against this background, the political elite, largely formed during the Soviet period, was not interested in fundamentally changing the rules of the game. The inertia of post-Soviet power structures was extremely strong. Moreover, democratisation efforts were accompanied by these elites attempting to maintain their privileges and influence. A well-known report by the Atlantic Council (2019) emphasises that corrupt practices have become a systemic governance tool for maintaining formal control over the state apparatus, hindering the development of democratic institutions and the rule of law.

The lack of trust in state institutions, such as the parliament, courts, the police and executive authorities, also requires special attention. Studies in recent decades have shown that these institutions have often remained symbols of the repressive past or instruments for the private enrichment of elites, rather than servants of the public interest. This level of mistrust hindered the consolidation of a new social contract based on trust, cooperation and shared responsibility (Kulyk, 2017; Riabchuk, 2019). For example, a study published only in Ukrainian, by the Razumkov Center (2016) reports that trust in courts and the prosecutor's office hovers only 10% of the population.

In addition, political narratives in independent Ukraine have gradually become radicalised, ideologised and polarised. It is important to note that although radical right-wing movements did not have significant electoral representation, they have become a symbolic factor actively exploited by Russian propaganda to delegitimise Ukrainian statehood. The Kremlin used the existence of even marginal radical right-wing groups as a pretext to justify the concept of 'denazification', one of the main propaganda slogans of the aggression against Ukraine Shekhovtsov (2016).

Thus, political inclusion, as well as the fight against internal and external manifestations of marginalisation, have become key challenges for the modern social contract. As noted in the essays of the Aspen Institute (2024), the country's social contract should consider issues of pluralism, participation, fair representation and cultural diversity. Without the integration of these principles into the structure of social relations, democratic transformation will remain more formal than substantive.

Political, social and economic inequalities

The key points in the transformation of the social contract in Ukraine were two recent events: the Orange Revolution (2004) and the Revolution of Dignity (2013-2014). For context, the Orange Revolution (2004) asserted citizens' fundamental right to freely elect their authorities, contesting electoral fraud in the presidential race and affirming the democratic principle of political representation. Concomitantly, the Revolution of Dignity (2013–2014) advanced a deeper claim: the right of the nation to determine its civilizational trajectory, rejecting external coercion in favour of European integration and democratic governance. In both movements, civil society emerged as the principal actor and decisive subject, mobilizing diverse social groups, sustaining peaceful protest, and articulating collective demands. Civil society actors also became key promoters of transforming Ukraine's social contract, dismantling previous authoritarian legacies and forging new democratic norms grounded in popular sovereignty and civic agency. They not only manifested public dissatisfaction with authoritarianism and corruption but also marked a paradigm shift in the relationship between the state and society. As Yevhen Hlibovytskyi notes, "Maidan was a protest against institutional failure – for the first time, citizens en masse declared that the source of legitimacy was not the government, but society" (Aspen Institute, 2024).

Volunteering became the most vivid embodiment of the transforming social contract: citizens ceased to be mere recipients of services, and instead emerged as co-creators of the public good... self-organized initiatives in healthcare, logistics, defence, and information security formed the backbone of a parallel civil state... (Hrytsak, 2023, p. 44)

The Maidans became a symbol representing a new type of civic mobilisation, where horizontal structures, volunteer movements, self-organisation and inclusiveness formed a new fabric of the social contract. Citizen participation in the protests was not only a political action, but also an act of creating a new type of social solidarity based on the values of dignity, justice, mutual support and the right to vote.

The role of civil society in Ukraine has grown significantly since 2014. Protests, activism, independent media, anti-corruption initiatives and public scrutiny have become mechanisms of public influence on the authorities and tools for democratising social space. At the same time, as noted by Mykhailo Minakov (2018) and Andrew Wilson (2017), Ukrainian civil society has become both an object of public pressure and a platform for generating alternative political discourses that can influence institutional changes.

The Maidans thus emerged as an outburst of resistance and critical rethinking of the political community, an attempt to build an alternative architecture of the social contract based on

moral responsibility, ethical choice and self-organisation. This experience has become the basis for a new model of coexistence in Ukraine, which will only intensify in the context of war and crisis of statehood.

Russia's full-scale invasion in 2022 was not only a breakdown of the geopolitical status quo, but also a profound impetus to rethink the nature of the social contract in Ukraine. Previously, social relations between the state and its citizens had remained fragmented and under-institutionalised. However, the war created conditions in which the social contract became an object of everyday practice – in the form of mutual solidarity, resource mobilisation and ethical unity.

As Yaroslav Hrytsak notes: "the war created a new contract – one based on responsibility, sacrifice and solidarity" (Hrytsak, 2023). This contract is formed not only through institutions of power, but also through everyday practices of support, assistance, resistance and interaction. It emerges as a bottom-up response to fundamental challenges – the preservation of statehood, the protection of life and national dignity. The phenomenon of 'civic mobilisation' – the active participation of millions of people in voluntary, humanitarian, educational and defensive initiatives – signals a new type of citizenship in Ukraine. War has intensified: the development of horizontal interaction structures; the restoration of local political subjectivity, and the strengthening of identification with the state as an institution of hope rather than fear. War updates the role of the state as a guarantor of survival, security and unity. In such circumstances, the state acts as a 'Leviathan' – a powerful tool for stabilising society. However, it is important that this power does not turn into authoritarianism. It is civil society that plays a balancing role here, preventing the authorities from monopolising the new contract (RAND, 2023; Kuzio, 2015).

The war in Ukraine has unleashed a profound social, humanitarian and environmental crisis that is significantly altering the content and meaning of the social contract. Social structures are already fragile due to the post-imperial and post-Soviet legacy, as well as the long-lasting distrust of institutions in the country. These structures have been exposed to new pressures and challenges under the influence of the war, requiring a systemic response from both the state and civil society. New social inequalities have emerged due to massive internal displacement (according to the UN, over 5 million Internally Displaced People – IDP) and destruction of housing and infrastructure, as well as limited access to healthcare, education and basic services. The war has exacerbated regional disparities and caused new waves of marginalisation of certain groups (e.g., women, children, the elderly, people with disabilities, IDP and veterans). Social challenges are also exacerbated by the moral trauma of war – losses, psychological stress and the experience of violence and occupation. In addition to its

social impact, the war has had catastrophic environmental consequences that must be fully integrated into the new model of social contract.

The social contract in Ukraine is undergoing a profound transformation under the influence of historical, social and geopolitical factors. From the colonial-authoritarian model of citizen-state interaction inherited from empires and the Soviet regime, Ukrainian society is gradually moving towards a model based on solidarity, civic participation, dignity and responsibility. This process has intensified particularly after the Revolution of Dignity, when civil society strongly acclaimed that Ukrainians are aspiring to join NATO and EU, and in the context of the all-out Russian invasion of 2022, which became a catalyst for the renewed moral, ethical and institutional content of the social contract.

Today, a new social contract is being formed in Ukraine at three key levels: 1) between the state and its citizens in the form of active participation and mutual responsibility; 2) between different social groups, taking into account the principles of justice, inclusion and social protection; 3) between Ukraine and the international community as part of the global space of democracy, security and sustainable development.

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